

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office
2800 Cottage Way, Room W-2605
Sacramento, California 95825-1846

IN REPLY REFER TO:
1-1-01-F-0314

July 5, 2002

Mr. Calvin C. Fong
Chief, Regulatory Branch
(Attn: Molly Martindale)
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
333 Market Street
San Francisco, California 94105-2197

Subject: Formal Endangered Species Consultation on the Santa Clara Valley Water District Ten-Year Maintenance Permit, PN 22525S

Dear Mr. Fong:

This is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) May 16, 2001, request for formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the Santa Clara Valley Water District's Ten-Year Maintenance Permit in Santa Clara County, California. Your request was received in our office on May 16, 2001. This document represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the action on the following threatened and endangered species, in accordance with section 7 of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (Act): the threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) (red-legged frog), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (harvest mouse), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) (clapper rail), threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) (snowy plover), endangered least Bell's vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*) (vireo), threatened bay checkerspot butterfly (*Euphydryas editha bayensis*) (bay checkerspot), endangered Santa Clara Valley dudleya (*Dudleya setchellii*) (dudleya), endangered Metcalf Canyon jewelflower (*Streptanthus albidus* ssp. *albidus*) (jewelflower), endangered Coyote ceanothus (*Ceanothus ferrisae*) (ceanothus), and endangered Tiburon paintbrush (*Castilleja affinis* ssp. *neglecta*) (paintbrush).

This biological opinion is based on information provided in (1) the September 2001 Biological Assessment; (2) the March 2001 Draft Stream Maintenance Program document; (3) the March 28, 2001, Draft Environmental Impact Report (DEIR); (3) the October 31, 2001, Corps Public Notice; (4) the August 2001 Final Environmental Impact Report (FEIR); (6) the February 20, 2002, Appendices for the Final Permit Package; (7) numerous meetings, telephone conversations, and field investigations with staff from the District, the Corps, and the Service; (8) numerous meetings, telephone conversations, and field

investigations with other Federal and State agencies involved with the permit; and (9) information contained in Service files. A complete administrative record of this consultation is on file in this office.

Consultation History

March 28, 2001: The District provided the Draft Environmental Impact Report (DEIR) and Draft Stream Maintenance Program (SMP) to the Service.

May 9, 2001: The Service provided comments to the District on the DEIR and Draft SMP.

May 16, 2001: The Corps requested initiation of formal consultation on the Program and provided a Draft Biological Assessment to the Service.

August 9, 2001: The Service requested additional information from the Corps.

October 12, 2001: The Corps provided the Final Biological Assessment and initiated formal consultation.

February 20, 2002: The District provided additional information on conservation measures to protect endangered species.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Corps proposes to issue a 10-year Regional Permit pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act to the District for its Stream Maintenance Program (SMP) for implementation of routine stream maintenance projects. The need for maintenance arises from past modifications to natural streams and from land use changes in these watersheds. The District routinely removes sediment and vegetation from streams, canals, and associated facilities to achieve their desired capacity for water conveyance. Vegetation also is removed from streams and canals to provide vehicle access and fire prevention. The District conducts bank protection to restore eroded flood protection facilities and protect property. The SMP includes a regional mitigation program to compensate for wetland, riparian, and endangered species habitat loss. The District has jurisdiction over 828 miles of streams and canals in the Santa Clara basin and Pajaro River basin, of which 300 miles are considered “unmodified” stream channels, that is, streams that have not been channelized as part of an official flood control project.

The District manages streams, canals, reservoirs, dams, pipelines, groundwater percolation facilities, and water treatment plants. Stream maintenance is required to meet the District’s flood protection and water supply objectives. Sediment removal, vegetation management and bank protection typically are ongoing processes, and the facilities do not function as intended without maintenance. Routine maintenance is undertaken in streams and canals and adjacent to District

property and easements. The District's jurisdiction on a stream begins at the point where 320 acres (0.5 square mile) of watershed drain to the stream and continues downstream to San Francisco Bay or the limits of the Pajaro River in Santa Clara County. The District's jurisdiction consists of 191 streams for approximately 828 miles and 10 canals for approximately 41 miles.

Work areas for the SMP are primarily downstream of dams with a few locations above reservoirs. The scope of the SMP is limited to routine maintenance of existing facilities and waterways in the geographic area described above. New flood control projects not considered routine maintenance are subject to separate section 7 consultation under the Act. Baseline conditions for the analysis are those that currently exist on streams in the project work areas. Generally, these areas have been subjected to years of prior maintenance. Any proposed stream maintenance outside the area in this analysis or other activities excluded from the SMP will be evaluated under separate environmental review and permitting process.

Work Projections and Planning Horizon

Projections for future work under the SMP is based on analysis of historical data going back to 1977. All forms of maintenance show a consistent pattern, although projections of future stream maintenance cannot represent the exact extent of work that will occur. Some future routine maintenance may occur outside of the District's projected work areas that is still consistent with the general impacts of the program. Maintenance at these sites will be included in the SMP as long as it does not result in environmental effects substantially greater than those evaluated for the whole SMP.

Several activities are not included in the SMP. Emergency repairs are for protection of life, health, property, or essential public service from clear and imminent danger. Large construction projects and Capital Improvement Projects are not considered routine stream maintenance and are not addressed. In addition, other District maintenance activities that are not routine, are not located within or next to streams or canals, or alter design flood conveyance or capacity are not included. Maintenance of groundwater percolation ponds, instream summer dams, reservoirs, major dams, pipelines outside of stream corridors, and installation/modification of fish ladders are not included. The following maintenance activities are excluded from the SMP because they are located where insufficient environmental information is available, high environmental sensitivity exists, or the magnitude of the activity is greater than is reasonably considered routine maintenance: (1) sediment removal and vegetation management above 1,000 feet elevation and above reservoirs; (2) hardscape bank protection in high quality fisheries habitat or high quality riparian habitat; and (3) sediment removal, wetland vegetation control, or removal of in-channel trees in Llagas Creek downstream of highway 152 to the confluence with the Pajaro River and the Pajaro River within Santa Clara County.

Sediment Removal

Most routine sediment removal responds to stream conditions that reflect geomorphic instability. Sediment is removed from both tidal and non-tidal channels and is conducted to maintain the

capacity of District flood protection facilities and is conducted most frequently in engineered or modified channels. The headwaters of Santa Clara County streams are steep and contain erosive terrain that produce high volumes of sediment. Urban development and historic land uses such as grazing increase the sediment loads and runoff volumes in these streams. The mountain and foothill streams emerge onto alluvial fans, where rapid reductions in channel slope and increases in floodplain width cause sediment deposition. If left undisturbed, alluvial streams of the valley floor would transport sediment through processes of point bar building and lateral erosion in meandering channels. Urban development constrains many stream systems in Santa Clara County, their natural hydraulic functions. Flood channel design is based on water capacity rather than ability to transport sediment. Sediment tends to accumulate repeatedly in areas where the stream gradient flattens in the valley floor. These areas require routine removal of sediment to maintain flood capacity. Flood protection channels are designed to maximize flow area, and maintenance prevents them from achieving geomorphic stability. To reduce impacts to wetlands and red-legged frog habitat, crews will remove sediment and vegetation from one side of the channel each year. Sediment also is removed from natural creeks occasionally to maintain capacity of outfalls, culverts, bridges, and stream gauging stations. This technique reduces wetland impacts while preventing long-term vegetative succession.

The District has estimated that an average of 80,000 cubic yards of sediment on 16 miles of nontidal channel will be removed annually from both concrete-lined and earth-lined channels. The total sediment removal area projected over the course of the program is approximately 60 miles of stream. Sediment removal from canals is estimated to be less than 1,000 cubic yards per year and can occur anywhere between levee slopes. Annual sediment removal will vary depending on rainfall conditions of the previous season.

Tidal channels are subject to sedimentation through a combination of wind entrainment and tidal inflows of bay mud. Rising tides bring mud into the channels, and the mud settles and remains as the tides go out. Tidal prisms in the South Bay are lower than historic levels due to extensive diking of former tidal marshes, hampering the tides' ability to transport sediment. Sediment removal to maintain channel capacity in tidal channels prevents the establishment of equilibrium of erosion and deposition. Accretion rates at sediment removal sites vary widely. Some sites will require sediment removal only once, others will be cleared several times. The District excavates accumulated mud from tidal channels to maintain flow capacity. Routine maintenance of tidal channels is limited to short reaches of the Guadalupe River, San Tomas Aquino, Calabazas, Permanente, Stevens, Matadero, and San Francisquito Creeks, and Sunnyvale East and West Channels. Over the course of the permit, a total of 29 acres of tidal wetlands are expected to be affected by sediment removal, and 1 acre of tidal wetlands is expected to be affected by vegetation management.

Typically, sediment is removed using excavators, draglines, loaders, and dump trucks. The method used to remove sediment depends upon channel configuration and geometry, equipment reach and rate of removal, channel type (tidal or non-tidal, concrete or earth bottom), moisture content of the sediment, ramp location, and access road width. Concrete-lined channels may be cleaned by pushing sediment into a pile with a bulldozer and/or removing the sediment using an

excavator. Sediment is disposed at an approved site. Saturated sediment may be temporarily placed adjacent to the work site to dry before being removed to a disposal site. To remove sediment from channels that will not support equipment, such as tidal sloughs, a dragline or excavator is positioned on the top of the bank. Most often, sediment removal is implemented in the dry season (June 15-October 15). If water must be bypassed around the site during work, water pumps, pipes, and cofferdams may be used. In some cases, a bypass channel or detention basin may be used to isolate a site. Temporary access roads and ramps may need to be constructed during sediment removal.

Vegetation Management

Vegetation management typically has one of three purposes: flood channel maintenance, invasive species control, and native plant promotion. Management of vegetation in and adjacent to creeks and canals is necessary to maintain the flood and transport capacity in channels and canals. Dense vegetation affects the ability of the channel to contain the volume of flood waters for which it was designed. Depending on the original design and the characteristics of the channel, the frequency of vegetation management varies from annually to every few years. Vegetation management for environmental purposes includes control of invasive non-native plants. The District also controls weeds at revegetation sites to increase the number of native trees and shrubs and to establish self-sustaining native plant communities. The District manages vegetation for other purposes including the elimination of plant roots from levees and concrete channels linings; controlling combustible weeds and grasses to meet local fire codes; providing visual clearance to inspect facilities; and providing access along maintenance roads.

The District has revised vegetation management approaches continually over the past 30 years. The three main methods of vegetation management are hand removal (chain saws, weed-eaters, *etc*); mechanical removal (moving and discing); and chemical control with herbicides. A method or combination of methods is chosen for each site depending on the maintenance requirements of the facility. Efficiency, economics, and protection of public health and environmental resources are considered in the selection of methods. The two types of in-channel vegetation management are herbicide application and hand removal. Weeds, shrubs, and trees are removed by hand where it is not possible to access the area with spraying or mowing equipment. Trees with trunk diameters up to 6 inches diameter at breast height (dbh) are removed by hand. Vegetation often is sprayed with herbicides, and then approximately 6 months later, the dead material is removed by hand. Hand removal of dead vegetation is necessary when herbicide spraying is new to an area and a large amount of vegetation needs to be removed. In subsequent years, vegetative regrowth is reduced and little to no follow-up hand removal is necessary.

Upland vegetation management occurs on all land above channel bottoms such as levee or bank tops, slopes, benches, and maintenance roads. Upland areas are not seasonally inundated by water and are vegetated with upland plants, primarily annual grasses or shrubs. The vegetation management methods in upland areas are discing, mowing, herbicide application, and hand removal. Discing is conducted to create firebreaks and eliminates or reduces grasses that cause a summer fire hazard. Mowing occurs one to three times annually at each location, usually

between May and October. Herbicides are sprayed on levees and unpaved maintenance roads, and along some property lines. On levees, herbicides primarily keep woody vegetation and broadleaf weeds from establishing where they will interfere with flood capacity or hinder their inspection. Weeds and grasses are sprayed on maintenance roads to define and clear the access route. Herbicide spraying along property lines assists in establishing a firebreak. Herbicides are sprayed from a truck-mounted rig or a controlled drop applicator. The District removes vegetation by hand in upland areas where mowers cannot access, and herbicides are impractical or not allowed. Hand removal of vegetation is generally used in upland areas along fire lines to establish fire breaks. Overhanging growth is removed by pruning tree branches that impede access roads.

The frequency of vegetation management activities varies from semiannually to once every several years, depending on the method used. Generally, vegetation management in channels is conducted once a year. Channel herbicide work is conducted throughout the summer dry season from July 1 through October 15. Hand removal is conducted near the end of the growing season in November and December. Some adjustment to these time periods can occur to protect nesting birds and anadromous fish.

The targeted vegetation management area consists of approximately 2,000 acres. However, the actual area of treatment is much smaller. Vegetation management work will occur on 120 acres along 212 miles of stream channels (75 acres of treated area on 166 miles in the Santa Clara Basin, and 45 acres of treated area on 46 miles in the Pajaro Basin). Six acres are treated along 27 miles of canals. Vegetation management is performed on 1,894 acres of upland. Upland vegetation management is outside of the area of inundation, and generally has a buffer of grass or vegetation on the slopes between the right-of-way and the stream. Vegetation management is consistent from year to year, with some variation in flood protection activities due to weather patterns.

Historically, increases in some work activities have occurred during drought years, due to the absence of scouring effects of flood flows. Right-of-way activities remain constant regardless of weather patterns.

The District will continue to use herbicides as the primary method of controlling vegetation in the Santa Clara Basin. Because of concerns regarding environmental effects to wetlands, herbicide use in the Pajaro basin will be limited to upland areas, levee slopes, maintenance roads, fire breaks, and upland and channel areas supporting exotic plants. Herbicides are sprayed selectively at the plants targeted for removal. In streambeds where the removal of woody plants is required, only saplings smaller than 2 in. dbh are treated with herbicides. On uplands, herbicides are sprayed on maintenance roads to provide clear access and on levee slopes to eliminate broadleaf weeds. District staff routinely review new and changed herbicide formulations and changed label limitations. The District uses criteria for product selection that minimizes work, public health risk, and environmental impact. Herbicides applications follow guidelines from the EPA Bulletin, *Protecting Endangered Species, Interim Measures for Use of Pesticides in Santa Clara County* (EPA 2000). The bulletin provides a list of pesticide use

limitations meant to avoid impacts to listed species. The District will implement measures to avoid or minimize impacts of herbicides on non-target species.

Bank Protection

Bank protection involves both erosion repair and erosion prevention. The District will repair stream banks when the erosion causes the following problems: (1) potential damage to property; (2) public safety risk; (3) damage to transportation, utilities, or recreation; (4) damage to water quality and aquatic wildlife; (5) damage to riparian habitat and riparian wildlife. Structures will range from hard (*i.e.*, rock blankets, concrete, sack concrete, gabions) to soft (willow brush mattresses, log crib walls, pole plantings) or a combination of the two. Bank protection also includes maintenance to prevent future erosion, which can reduce sedimentation and improve water quality.

Stream erosion occurs because of hydraulic forces or geotechnical instabilities and can be accelerated by human intervention. Accelerated erosion is typically a result of land uses that affect the stream corridor, including grazing, agriculture, and construction. Increases in impermeable surfaces in a watershed (roofs, roads) alter stormwater runoff patterns, resulting in higher peak flows and shorter runoff times.

Typically the District conducts some form of bank repair at 30 to 50 sites each year over an average of one linear mile. Approximately 70% of bank protection work will be done on unmodified channels and 30% on modified channels. The quantity and location of bank protection activities vary greatly from year to year based on watershed conditions, degree of safety hazard, work load, budget, and quantity of other priority work. Historical bank protection has concentrated primarily in cities and semi-rural foothills of the Santa Clara Valley. Many areas receiving bank protection are devoid of native riparian vegetation as a consequence of erosion.

No more than 50% of future bank protection projects will be hardscape, which precludes the establishment of riparian vegetation. District policy emphasizes limiting hardscape to the extent practicable, particularly in unmodified channels with riparian habitat. The District will mitigate the effects of partial softscape designs at a 1:1 ratio and impervious hardscape at a 3:1 ratio of offsite riparian restoration. Repair of old erosion control structures will provide opportunities to improve design and incorporate environmental benefits. Design specifics include evaluation of bank slope, shear stress, soil type, flow velocity, and adjacent channel dimensions. Each site is evaluated for revegetation potential. Equipment used for bank protection may include excavators, bulldozers, cranes, and loaders. Water will be bypassed around the sites during repair work, water pumps and piping, and cofferdams of earth, gravel, sandbags, hay bales, rubber or other suitable material. Most often, bank protection projects are implemented in the dry season. The average duration of bank protection work is 10 working days and generally occurs between June 15 and October 15.

Other Stream Maintenance

Other stream maintenance includes the following activities: trash removal at trash racks and other areas; repair and installation of fences and gates; grading and other repairs to restore access roads and levees; grading small unvegetated areas to improve drainage and reduce erosion; repair of structure with in-kind materials (concrete linings, culverts, pipes, or valves); cleaning and minor sediment removal at drains, tide gates, fish ladders, and fish screens; tree pruning, irrigation, and weeding at mitigation sites; removal of obstruction and sediment within 100 feet of stream crossings, outfalls, and drop structures; and rodent control with smoke bombs, pesticides and traps.

District staff will submit an annual report detailing all maintenance work for the previous year. Sediment removal, vegetation management, and bank protection work which have been repeated under the SMP will be distinguished from areas where such work is being undertaken for the first time under the SMP. The District will evaluate the need to modify BMPs and work practices each year and summarize future modifications in the report. The District also will report on all mitigation implemented for each year, including maps showing mitigation site locations, a description of the stage of planning and implementation schedule; progress towards success criteria, and a summary of maintenance at mitigation sites. The District will provide the results of all listed species surveys to the Service and DFG. For the first five years of the program, the District will provide the agencies with a tour of representative work areas for that year and all mitigation sites.

Conservation and Minimization Measures

Conservation measures include general and specific practices for resource protection termed Best Management Practices (BMP), mitigation for bank protection, vegetation loss and special-status species impacts. BMPs are adapted to meet the anticipated need for maintenance-specific mitigation and are listed in Table 1. The following additional conservation/minimization measures are proposed:

1. No sediment removal will occur in tidal channels during clapper rail breeding season (D. Padley, pers. comm. 2001). Other maintenance work in tidal areas will be conducted at least 500 feet away from suitable clapper rail breeding habitat during the clapper rail breeding season. Sediment removal equipment will work from the stream bank. If clapper rails are observed in the work area, they will be chased away to appropriate habitat to allow work to proceed.
2. The District anticipates that 11 acres of clapper rail habitat will be lost during sediment removal from tidal channels. The District will restore at least 120 acres of a 310-acre salt pond (Pond A4) to tidal marsh and credit 30 acres of this site to compensate for lost clapper rail habitat. Design and planning of this restoration will begin in 2006.
3. The District has identified 6 watersheds where the program would affect red-legged frogs. To determine the area of effects to red-legged frogs, the District assessed areas of habitat (H.T. Harvey 1997). District staff determined that impacts would occur to approximately 29.3 acres of red-legged frog habitat. To compensate for these effects, the District has proposed to set aside 108 acres of watershed lands as a red-legged frog preserve. In addition, the District will protect 712 to 972 acres of stream and associated upland habitat as open space through their Stream and Watershed Protection Program.

4. Bank stabilization and sediment removal project sites will be surveyed for red-legged frogs prior to construction. If red-legged frogs are found at the project site, a qualified biologist will capture them and relocate them to suitable habitat. Barrier fences will be constructed to prevent the frogs from re-entering the work sites until construction is completed.
5. The District will mitigate hardscape bank stabilization projects at a ratio of 3 linear feet of offsite restored riparian corridor for every 1 linear foot of hardscape installed. Bank stabilization projects that are a mix of hardscape and plantings will be mitigated at a ratio of 1 to 1.
6. The District will continue their routine surveys to obtain data on the distribution and abundance of special-status species. The District maintains databases for several special-status species in the action area. District staff have conducted clapper rail surveys in tidal marsh habitat since 1996. Occupied clapper rail sites will be surveyed annually. Other suitable habitat will be surveyed once every five years. Known red-legged frog occurrences will be surveyed annually. Since 1997, vireo surveys have been conducted weekly along Llagas Creek during May and June. These surveys will continue for the duration of the permit.
7. The District will remove 125 acres of giant reed (*Arundo donax*) from streams and riparian areas over a period of 10 years. Areas requiring revegetation will be planted with native species. Sites will receive herbicide treatment, followed by monitoring and follow-up herbicide treatment as necessary. The District will credit 66 acres of reed removal as compensation for impacts to riparian vegetation and 59 acres to compensate for temporal losses of habitat that occurs between maintenance impacts and mitigation installation. Giant reed occurrences will be mapped.
8. To prevent impacts to serpentine plants, sediment removed from channels in serpentine areas will not be stockpiled on site. A qualified botanist will survey all project sites in serpentine areas during the appropriate time of the year to identify the species present. Areas supporting sensitive serpentine plant or animal species will be permanently marked in the field and protected by a 100-foot buffer zone. No upland herbicides will be used within these buffer zones.
9. No lethal rodent control methods will be used within the range of the harvest mouse.
10. Each November, the District will evaluate the program. BMPs will be modified as necessary to improve environmental protection of stream resources.
11. To minimize potential impacts to the least Bell's vireo, sediment removal in Llagas Creek above Highway 152 will be limited to areas directly under and adjacent to bridges. The only vegetation removal that will occur will be the removal of giant reed for riparian habitat restoration purposes.

Action Area

The action area for the proposed program encompasses all streams and their adjacent banks in the Santa Clara Basin and the Pajaro River basin within Santa Clara County, and all other wetland, salt pond, and upland areas directly and indirectly affected by program activities.

Status of the Species

California Red-legged Frog

The red-legged frog was federally listed as threatened (61 **FR** 25813) effective June 24, 1996. A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the red-legged frog is presented in the *Draft Recovery Plan for the California Red-legged Frog (Rana aurora draytonii)* (Service 2000). This species is the largest native frog in the western United States (Wright and Wright 1949), ranging from 4 to 13 centimeters (cm) (1.5 to 5.1 inches [in.]) (Stebbins

1985). The abdomen and hind legs of adults are largely red; the back is characterized by small black flecks and larger irregular dark blotches. Dorsolateral folds are prominent on the back. Larvae (tadpoles) range from 14 to 80 millimeters (mm) (0.6 to 3.1 in.) in length, and the body color is dark brown and yellow with darker spots (Storer 1925).

Breeding sites have been documented in a variety of aquatic habitats. Larvae, juveniles and adult frogs inhabit streams, ponds, marshes, pools and backwaters within streams, dune ponds, lagoons, estuaries, and artificial impoundments such as stock ponds. Breeding has been documented in these habitat types irrespective of vegetative cover. Frogs often breed successfully in artificial ponds and stream reaches with little or no emergent or riparian vegetation. The importance of riparian vegetation for this species is not well understood. It is believed the moisture and camouflage provided by the riparian plant community may provide foraging habitat and may facilitate dispersal and provide pools and backwater aquatic areas for breeding. Other factors are more likely to influence the suitability of aquatic breeding sites, such as the general lack of introduced aquatic predators. Red-legged frogs often disperse from their breeding habitat to utilize various aquatic, riparian, and upland habitats. When riparian habitat is present, frogs rest and feed in the vegetation. When riparian habitat is absent, frogs spend considerable time resting and feeding under rocks and ledges both in and out of water. Red-legged frogs also use small mammal burrows, moist leaf litter, and incised stream channels with portions narrower and deeper than 18 in. (Service 2000a).

Red-legged frogs disperse upstream and downstream of their breeding sites to forage and seek sheltering habitat. Sheltering habitat potentially includes all aquatic, riparian, and upland areas within the range of the species and any landscape features that provide cover, such as existing animal burrows, boulders or rocks, organic debris such as downed trees or logs, and industrial debris. Agricultural features such as drains, watering troughs, spring boxes, or hay ricks also may be used. Accessibility to sheltering habitat is essential for the survival of red-legged frogs within a watershed and can be a factor limiting population numbers and survival. During winter rain events, juvenile and adult red-legged frogs are known to disperse up to 1-2 km overland (Service 2000a).

Female frogs deposit egg masses on emergent vegetation so the egg mass floats on the surface of the water (Hayes and Miyamoto 1984). Red-legged frogs breed from November through March with earlier breeding records occurring in southern localities (Storer 1925). Individuals occurring in coastal drainages are active year-round (Jennings *et al.* 1992), whereas those found in interior sites are normally less active during the cold season. Red-legged frogs lay their eggs during or shortly after large rainfall events in late winter and early spring (Hayes and Miyamoto 1984). Eggs hatch in 6 to 14 days (Jennings 1988). Siltation during the breeding season can cause asphyxiation of eggs and small larvae. Larvae undergo metamorphosis 3.5 to 7 months after hatching (Storer 1925, Wright and Wright 1949, Jennings and Hayes 1990). Of the various life stages, larvae probably experience the highest mortality rates, with less than 1 percent of eggs laid reaching metamorphosis (Jennings *et al.* 1992). Sexual maturity normally is reached at 3 to 4 years of age (Storer 1925, Jennings and Hayes 1985). Red-legged frogs may live 8 to 10 years (Jennings *et al.* 1992).

The diet of red-legged frogs is highly variable. Hayes and Tennant (1985) found invertebrates to be the most common food items. Vertebrates, such as Pacific tree frogs (*Hyla regilla*) and California mice (*Peromyscus californicus*), represented over half the prey mass eaten by larger frogs (Hayes and Tennant 1985). Hayes and Tennant (1985) found juvenile frogs to be active diurnally and nocturnally, whereas adult frogs were largely nocturnal. Feeding activity probably occurs along the shoreline and on the surface of the water (Hayes and Tennant 1985).

Several nonnative species reduce the quality of aquatic habitat for the red-legged frog through predation and competition. Researchers in central California have noted the decline and eventual disappearance of red-legged frog populations once bullfrogs became established at the same site. Twedt (1993) documented bullfrog predation of juvenile northern red-legged frogs and suggested that bullfrogs could prey on subadult red-legged frogs as well. In addition to predation, bullfrogs may have a competitive advantage over red-legged frogs: bullfrogs are larger, possess more generalized food habits (Bury and Whelan 1984), possess an extended breeding season (Storer 1933) and are unpalatable to predatory fish as larvae (Kruse and Francis 1977). Bullfrogs also interfere with red-legged frog reproduction. Both California and northern red-legged frogs have been observed in amplexus with (mounted

on) both male and female bullfrogs (Jennings and Hayes 1990, Twedt 1993, M. Jennings, in litt. 1993). Red swamp crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*), signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), and several other species of warm water fish including mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) (L. Hunt, in litt. 1993, S. Barry, in litt. 1992, S. Sweet, in litt. 1993) prey upon red-legged frog larvae.

California red-legged frogs spend most of their lives in and near sheltered backwaters of ponds, marshes, springs, streams, and reservoirs. These types of environments are particularly vulnerable to mercury contamination due to favorable conditions for the conversion of inorganic mercury to methyl mercury. Several hundred abandoned mercury mines of varying sizes and states of remediation or disrepair currently contaminate the coast of California with both inorganic and methyl mercury. The Almaden mine in Santa Clara County drains to Alamitos Creek in the Guadalupe watershed. Red-legged frogs have been sighted in the Alamitos watershed. This mine presents potential exposure pathways for mercury to the habitat of the red-legged frog. Mercury residue data in yellow-legged frogs downstream from abandoned mines in the Cache creek data cited above and provided in the mercury appendix indicate rapid frogs may bioaccumulate mercury in the vicinity of these mines (Service files).

Red-legged frogs have been extirpated from more than 70 percent of their historic range. Historically, this species was found throughout the Central Valley and Sierra Nevada foothills. Monterey, San Luis Obispo, and Santa Barbara counties support the largest extent of currently occupied habitat. Habitat loss, non-native species introduction, and urban encroachment are the primary factors that have adversely affected the red-legged frog throughout its range.

The draft recovery plan specifies that the status of the red-legged frog should be considered within recovery units as opposed to the overall range of the species to promote and protect the continued existence of viable metapopulations. A metapopulation is a group of spatially separated populations that can occasionally exchange dispersing individuals. The populations in a metapopulation typically undergo interdependent extinction and colonization, where individual populations may go extinct and later be recolonized from another population. Red-legged frog populations may also exhibit "pseudo-extinction," where the species is not found but nonetheless continues to inhabit a site and re-appears in a subsequent year.

The goal of the draft recovery plan is to protect the long-term viability of all extant populations within each recovery unit. Within each recovery unit, core areas have been delineated and represent contiguous areas of moderate to high red-legged frog densities that are relatively free of exotic species such as bullfrogs. Designating core areas protects metapopulations that, combined with suitable dispersal habitat, will promote long-term viability within existing populations. All stream maintenance work will be conducted outside the core recovery areas of Santa Clara County.

The Santa Clara Basin is located within the proposed South/East San Francisco Bay recovery unit, which extends from the northernmost portion of Contra Costa County, includes the eastern portion of San Mateo County, all of San Francisco County, and a portion of San Joaquin County south to Santa Clara County, including the Coyote Creek watershed (Service 2000). The Pajaro River basin and its tributaries are located within the Diablo Range/Salinas Valley recovery unit, which also includes the Panoche-San Luis, upper Gatos, Estrella, Tulare-Buena Vista Lakes,

Carrizo Plain, Alisal-Elkhorn Sloughs, and Salinas River watersheds. includes the Pajaro River basin and all its tributaries. The San Francisco Bay unit contains the largest number of occupied drainages in the northern portion of its range. Within this recovery unit, red-legged frogs have been nearly eliminated from urbanized lowland areas. The low-lying areas of Santa Clara County have been heavily urbanized. The frog still occurs in isolated populations in the foothills of the East Bay and Santa Clara Valley. Red-legged frogs are abundant in several areas in eastern Santa Clara County.

District staff have surveyed portions of the action area for red-legged frogs according to Service protocol. Approximately 80% of the streams in the action area with suitable habitat and available access to the District have been surveyed. Areas in the foothills and mountains have been less thoroughly surveyed due to difficulty accessing private land. Historical occurrences, currently occupied locations, and stream reaches that are considered unsuitable breeding habitat for the red-legged frog (Jennings 1997) are recorded in the District's database. The District has identified most of the county's ephemeral creeks thought to exclude red-legged frog breeding habitat, due to the absence of surface water during the tadpole rearing season. Historical occurrences, currently occupied locations, and stream reaches that are considered unsuitable breeding habitat are recorded in the District's database.

The Service considers the streams, wetlands, and uplands of the SMP area to have value as dispersal, resting, and feeding habitat for red-legged frogs. Levees with vegetation removed through herbicides and mechanical means are less likely to provide habitat for the frog than levees that are left undisturbed. Some potential exists for breeding red-legged frogs to reestablish themselves in low areas. Among the recovery tasks identified for Santa Clara County are protecting habitat and buffers from nearby urbanization and controlling non-native species. Other recovery actions common to all targeted watersheds, encompassing the project site, include but are not limited to the following: protect habitat, appropriately manage surface waters, reduce livestock impacts on riparian vegetation and water quality, reduce soil erosion to aquatic habitats, improve water quality, and use frog-compatible flood control planning.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The salt marsh harvest mouse was federally listed as endangered in 1970 (35 **FR** 16047). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the harvest mouse is presented in the *Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse & California Clapper Rail Recovery Plan* (Service 1984) and the references cited therein.

The harvest mouse is distinguished taxonomically into the northern and southern subspecies; *R. r. halicoetes* and *R. r. raviventris* respectively. The harvest mouse is an endemic rodent to the salt and brackish marshes of San Francisco Bay and adjacent tidally influenced areas. The historic range of the species included tidal marshes within San Francisco and San Pablo Bay, east to the Collinsville-Antioch areas. It has been estimated that about 30,100 acres currently remain (Dedrick 1993) in the Bay Area, approximately an 84 percent reduction in tidal wetlands since 1850. Agriculture, salt production, and urbanization have claimed most of the former tidal

marshes. At present, the distribution of the northern subspecies occurs along Suisun and San Pablo Bays north of Point Pinole in Contra Costa County and Point Pedro in Marin County. The southern subspecies is found in marshes in Corte Madera, Richmond, and South San Francisco Bay, mostly south of the San Mateo Bridge.

The harvest mouse has evolved to a life in tidal marshes. Specifically, they depend mainly on dense pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*) as their primary cover and food source. Harvest mice may utilize a broader source of food and cover which includes salt grass (*Distichlis spicata*) and other vegetation typically found in the salt and brackish marshes of this region. In natural systems, harvest mice can be found in the middle and upper tidal marsh and upland transition zones. Upland refugia is an essential habitat component during high tide events. The harvest mouse is highly dependent on cover, and open areas as small as 10 meters wide may act as barriers to movement (Shellhammer 1978, as cited in Service 1984). The harvest mouse does not utilize burrows. As described by Fisler (1965) in Service (1984), male harvest mice are reproductively active from April through September but may appear active throughout the year. Females are reproductively active from March to November and have a mean litter size of approximately 4 offspring.

The primary reason for harvest mouse decline is loss of habitat. The modern distribution of the salt marsh harvest mouse can be approximately inferred from two sources of data: the distribution of remaining suitable habitat and review of live-trapping surveys. Salt marsh harvest mice are distributed in Santa Clara County in tidal marshes in southern San Francisco Bay. Most major populations are subject to crashes (abrupt declines) or extirpation due to flooding (Service files). All major population centers of the southern subspecies are remote from one another. Specific locations include salt marshes adjacent to Coyote and Stevens Creeks, Alviso, Mayfield, and Guadalupe Sloughs, Palo Alto marsh and other locations dominated by dense pickleweed (District 2001-BA). The harvest mouse is probably intermittent or extirpated in Alviso (Service files). In the Palo Alto area, harvest mice are present at Alto Yacht Harbor marsh, locally within Palo Alto Baylands, and Laumeister-Faber marsh. The species is locally abundant at Renzel (ITT) Marsh, considered relatively stable managed habitat. A sparse, unstable population occurs in the Palo Alto Flood Basin (Service files). Restored salt marshes at Cooley's Landing are unlikely to support a new population for the next 2 decades. Charleston Slough and Stevens Creek salt marsh restorations are unlikely to be recolonized in the foreseeable future due to lack of suitable habitat. In eastern Santa Clara County, no major populations are known, but numerous small populations occur in fringing pickleweed marsh. The harvest mouse may be intermittently present in small populations or extirpated in fringing salt marsh patches around diked salt ponds. Small colonies or dispersing individuals may occur in pickleweed along interior dikes and ditches.

Ongoing high-magnitude wastewater discharges from sewage treatment operations and channelized urban runoff into tidal sloughs from San Jose to Milpitas are confined by salt pond dikes and impact fringing tidal marshes, rendering these areas, marginal at best, unsuitable. The depression of channel water salinity has converted tidal vegetative communities to brackish marsh with little to no habitat value to the harvest mouse (Duke *et al.* 1990).

The *Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse & California Clapper Rail Recovery Plan* (Service 1984) identifies various goals and objectives to recover and delist the species. In general it identifies the need to protect and enhance existing marshes and restore former habitat. The recovery strategy for the harvest mouse has general and geographic elements and is based on protection, enhancement, and restoration of habitat for the species.

Another action necessary for long-term conservation of the harvest mouse include a reduction in wastewater discharges into South Bay sloughs and improved surveys. Reduced discharges should be discharged diffusely in brackish microtidal lagoons and marsh edges (located in converted salt ponds) rather than at point in sloughs. Combined studies of vegetation structure, plant community composition, and harvest mouse live-trapping should be conducted over multiple years in all seasons at representative geographic subregions within the range of both subspecies. Salt marsh harvest mouse surveys should be shifted from site-specific, presence/absence surveys to systematic regional surveys with replicated sampling over time. Surveys should emphasize tracking harvest mouse populations both before and after major floods.

California clapper rail

The clapper rail was federally listed as endangered in 1970 (35 **FR** 16047). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the clapper rail is presented in the *Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse & California Clapper Rail Recovery Plan* (Service 1984) and the references cited therein. The clapper rail is endemic to tidally influenced salt and brackish marshes of California. Historically, the clapper rail occurred in tidal marshes along California's coast from Morro Bay, San Luis Obispo County to Humboldt Bay, Humboldt County. Currently, clapper rails are known to occur in tidal marshes in San Francisco, San Pablo, Grizzly, Suisun and Honker Bays.

The clapper rail is distinguishable from other rails by its large body size of 32-47 cm from bill to tail, and weighs approximately 250-350 g. It has a long, slightly decurved orange bill, a rufous breast, black and white barred flanks, and white undertail coverts (Ripley 1977). Clapper rails are sexually dimorphic, the males are slightly larger than females (Garcia 1995). Juveniles have a pale bill and dark plumage.

Clapper rails are typically found in the intertidal zone and sloughs of salt and brackish marshes dominated by Pacific cordgrass (*Spartina foliosa*), gumplant (*Grindelia spp.*), pickleweed, salt grass (*Distichlis spp.*), jaumea (*Jaumea carnosa*) and adjacent upland refugia. They also may occupy habitats with other vegetative components, which include, but are not limited to bulrush (*Scirpus americanus* and *S. Maritimus*), cattails (*Typha spp.*), and Baltic rush (*Juncus balticus*).

Clapper rails typically establish pairs during the month of February, and nesting typically occurs from March through August. Estimates of California clapper rail clutch size range from 5-14 eggs (DeGroot 1927, Gill 1972). The clapper rail builds a bowl shaped platform nest of marsh vegetation and detritus (DeGroot 1927, Zucca 1954, Gill 1972, Harvey 1980, Foerster *et al.*

1990, Garcia 1995). The clapper rail typically feeds on benthic invertebrates, but its diet is wide ranging, and includes seeds and occasionally small mammals such as the harvest mouse.

Similar to the harvest mouse, suitable habitat has been reduced by approximately 84 percent of historic in the San Francisco Bay Area due to habitat conversions for urban and agricultural uses and is a primary factor in the species decline. Additional impacts which have contributed to the decline in clapper rail populations include red fox predation, environmental contaminants, habitat conversion from effluent discharge, and erosion or subsidence of habitat.

During the 1980s, the clapper rail population in the eastern portion of the south Bay decreased substantially, from 400-500 individuals to 50-60 in 1991-92 (Harvey 1980, Service unpubl. data). Predation by the non-native red fox was apparently a major factor in this decline (Foerster and Takekawa 1991, Foerster *et al.* 1990). The most severe rail population declines and highest fox numbers were found in the east Bay marshes (*e.g.*, Dumbarton, Mowry, Ideal, and Calaveras). Winter airboat surveys in 1992-1993 documented a population increase in many south Bay marshes, in apparent response to predator control, which began in 1991 (Harding *et al.* 1998). Population estimates for east Bay marshes rose to 330 individuals in 1997-98. The most recent survey data indicate that rail populations on the east and west sides of the south Bay are approximately equal (Service unpubl. data).

In south San Francisco Bay, clapper rail populations presently occur in all of the larger tidal marshes. In Santa Clara county, rails occur along Alviso and Charleston Sloughs, and in outboard marshes of Moffett Field and Guadalupe Slough. The largest populations currently occur in Dumbarton and Mowry marshes in the east Bay, and in East Palo Alto and Greco in the west Bay. Clapper rails can also be found in salt marshes fringing the south Bay outboard of salt evaporation pond levees and along major tidal sloughs.

Western Snowy Plover

On March 5, 1993, the Pacific coast population of the western snowy plover was listed as threatened under provisions of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (58 **FR** 12864).

A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the snowy plover is presented in the *Western Snowy Plover (Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus) Pacific Coast Population Draft Recovery Plan* (Service 2001).

Although the majority of snowy plovers are site-faithful, returning to the same breeding site in subsequent breeding seasons, some also disperse within and between years (Warriner *et al.* 1986, Stenzel *et al.* 1994). Birds occasionally nest in the exact location as the previous year (Warriner *et al.* 1986). Snowy plovers renest readily after loss of their eggs (Wilson 1980, Warriner *et al.* 1986). After losing a clutch or brood or successfully hatching a nest, plovers may renest at the same site or move up to several hundred miles to nest at other sites (Stenzel *et al.* 1994, Powell *et al.* 1997). Renesting occurs 2 to 14 days after failure of a clutch and up to 5 renesting attempts have been observed for a pair (Warriner *et al.* 1986). The first chick hatched remains in or near the nest until other eggs (or at least the second egg) hatch. The adult plover, while incubating the eggs, also broods the first chick. Plover chicks are precocial, leaving the nest within hours after hatching to search for food. They are not able to fly for approximately 4 weeks after hatching; fledging requires 28 to 33 days (mean 31 days) (Warriner *et al.* 1986).

Western snowy plover numbers have declined on the U.S. Pacific coast over the past century. Habitat degradation caused by human disturbance, urban development, introduced beachgrass (*Ammophila* spp.), and expanding predator populations have resulted in a decline in active nesting areas and in the size of the breeding and wintering populations (Service 1993). In the south Bay, water diversion/impoundments, salt pond operations, impaired water quality, and natural factors (*e.g.* inclement weather) continue to affect the quality and quantity of snowy plover habitat (Service 1993). The reasons for decline and degree of threats vary by geographic location.

Water diversion and impoundment of creeks and rivers may negatively affect snowy plover habitat by reducing sand delivery to beaches and degrading water quality. Water diversions are a major threat to snowy plovers when they impair hydrologic processes (such as migration of creek and river mouths) that maintain open habitat at river and creek mouths by retarding the spread of introduced beachgrass (*Ammophila* spp.) and other vegetation. Water diversion, impoundment or stabilization activities could include construction of dams and irrigation, flood control and municipal water development projects.

Dry salt ponds of San Francisco Bay provide breeding and wintering habitat for snowy plovers. Dry salt ponds and unvegetated salt pond levees are used as plover nesting habitat. Ponds with shallow water provide important foraging habitat for plovers.

Within Santa Clara County, snowy plovers have been reported during the breeding season at the salt evaporator ponds adjacent to Guadalupe, Alviso, and Artesian (Mallard) Sloughs, and on

levees adjacent to Moffett Field. During the non-breeding season, they have been observed at Crittenden and Calabazas Marshes, salt ponds adjacent to Guadalupe and Alviso, Sloughs, and Coyote Creek (District 2001).

Critical habitat was established for the snowy plover on December 7, 1999 (64 **FR** 68508). In California, a total of 19 areas along the coast were designated as critical habitat areas. No critical habitat was designated for Santa Clara County where the project occurs.

It is not known whether the snowy plover historically nested in San Francisco Bay prior to the construction of salt evaporator ponds beginning in 1860 (Ryan and Parkin 1998). However, snowy plovers have wintered on San Francisco Bay since at least the late 1800s, as indicated by a specimen dated November 8, 1889, in the California Museum of Vertebrate Zoology (Grinnell *et al.* 1918). Surveys conducted during 1977-1980 estimated 1,593 adult snowy plovers along coastal California (Page and Stenzel 1981). As of 1980, the snowy plover had disappeared from significant parts of its coastal California breeding range. The decline was approximately 40 percent in San Francisco Bay. The most recent coast-wide survey was conducted in 1995, and suggested a further 17.3 percent decline in the number of breeding plovers. This constitutes an overall decline of 21 percent since the initial surveys of 1977-1980. Because San Francisco Bay was not surveyed in 1995, it is not known whether numbers there have changed from 1991 levels. When last surveyed in 1991, just over 200 adults were counted during the breeding season in San Francisco Bay. Almost all were in salt evaporation ponds in south San Francisco Bay.

Snowy plovers were recorded nesting on salt evaporation pond levees in Alviso as early as 1947 (Smith and Smith 1947). Breeding was confirmed in the Alviso salt ponds annually during the 1950s (Linsdale 1951, Sibley 1952, Cogswell 1956, Williams 1957, Cutler and Pugh 1959), with a high of 14 nests found in 1955 (Smith 1955). In 1971, Gill (1972) found nesting snowy plovers on the Knapp Gun Club property near the mouth of Alviso Slough. Page and Stenzel (1979) recorded snowy plovers in each of the three salt evaporation ponds bordering the south side of Alviso Slough (A6, A7, and A8).

Nesting snowy plovers have recently been recorded in salt evaporation ponds A6 and A8 (Ryan and Parkin 1988). Snowy plovers were observed in pond A6 every year between 1986 and 1994; breeding was confirmed during five of the nine years. Snowy plovers were also observed almost annually in pond A8 between 1981 and 1997; breeding was confirmed during nine of the 11 years. The San Francisco Bird Observatory did not conduct surveys on pond A8 in 1989 or 1993; however, incidental observations detected snowy plovers on the pond in both years (Corps 2000). In addition, H.T. Harvey and Associates surveyed pond A8 in 1998 and 1999, and observed nesting snowy plovers both years (Corps 2000).

Birders have observed snowy plovers foraging in the diked evaporation ponds on the northeast side of Alviso Slough (ponds A9-A12). However, these ponds usually contain water year round, making them unlikely places for plovers to nest. The only recent nesting record in the vicinity of these evaporation ponds consists of one to two pairs that have nested in some years in a small

impoundment between pond A12 and the railroad tracks, north of the Alviso marina (Corps 2000).

Least Bell's Vireo

The least Bell's vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*) was listed as endangered on May 2, 1986 (51 **FR** 16474). Critical habitat was designated on February 2, 1994 (59 **FR** 4845). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Draft Recovery Plan for the Least Bell's Vireo (Vireo bellii pusillus)* (Service 1998b).

The vireo is an obligate riparian species during the breeding season and prefers early successional habitat. It typically inhabits diverse woodlands along watercourses, including cottonwood-willow forests and oak woodlands. Adult vireos maintain territories that include upland areas for foraging. Vireos are insectivorous, preying on a wide variety of insects, particularly caterpillars. Foraging occurs at all levels of the riparian canopy but is concentrated at lower to middle strata. The vireo nests in dense cover 1-2 meters above ground and needs a dense, stratified canopy for foraging (Goldwasser 1981, Gray and Greaves 1981, Salata 1981, RECON 1989). Vireos arrive at breeding grounds from mid-March to early April and are generally present until late September. Brood parasitism by brown-headed cowbirds (*Molothrus ater*), predation, and human disturbance (vegetation clearing) are the primary reasons for nest failure.

Cowbird parasitism has exacerbated the decline caused by habitat loss and fragmentation. The vireo readily accepts cowbird eggs. Cowbirds achieve high population densities near vireo breeding sites as a result of land-use practices. Dairies, livestock grazing, equestrian centers, and golf courses provide foraging areas for cowbirds. If these facilities are located near rivers, cowbirds are easily able to infest vireo nests.

Prior to 1850, vireos were widespread and abundant in dense riparian areas throughout the Central Valley and other low elevations in California. The statewide population has declined drastically due to loss of riparian habitat and nest parasitism by brown-headed cowbirds (Service 1998b). Breeding populations now occur in eight southern California counties, with the majority of birds occurring in San Diego County. Many southern California populations are expanding or stable due to habitat protection and cowbird control programs (Service 1994). Since intensive cowbird removal programs were initiated in the late 1980s, the vireo population has increased dramatically. The vireo population increased from an estimated 300 pairs in 1986 to 1,346 pairs in 1996 (Service 1998b). Areas of suitable vireo habitat occur throughout Santa Clara County. A single nesting pair was seen adjacent to Llagas Creek upstream of the Pajaro River confluence. In May 2001, two males were heard singing along lower Llagas Creek (District 2001). A fledgling vireo was observed in Monterey County north of Salinas in the vicinity of Echo Valley in 2001 (District 2001).

Delisting of the vireo will require the re-establishment of a stable or increasing metapopulation in the upper Salinas Valley. Major recovery actions include habitat restoration and preservation

and cowbird control. Colonization of the Pajaro watershed was not anticipated in the Recovery Plan. However, riparian conservation and other recovery actions in the Pajaro Basin are important, as they could increase breeding in southern Santa Clara County and provide founding members for a population on the Salinas River.

Bay Checkerspot Butterfly

The bay checkerspot was listed as threatened on September 18, 1987, (52 **FR** 35366). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area* (Service 1998). The bay checkerspot is a medium-sized butterfly with a wing span of about 5 cm (2 in.). The forewings have black bands along all veins on upper wing surface, contrasting sharply with bright red, yellow and white spots.

Habitat of the bay checkerspot exists on shallow, serpentine-derived or similarly droughty and/or infertile soils, which support the butterfly's larval food plants, as well as nectar sources for adults. The primary larval host plant is dwarf plantain (*Plantago erecta*), a native annual. Bay checkerspot larvae (caterpillars) also may use a secondary host plant species; for example, when dwarf plantain dries up while pre-diapause larvae are still feeding. Purple owl's-clover (*Castilleja [Orthocarpus] densiflora*) and exserted paintbrush (*Castilleja exserta [Orthocarpus purpurascens]*) are common secondary host plants. Nectar plants for adults commonly visited include desertparsley (*Lomatium* spp.), California goldfields (*Lasthenia californica [=chrysostoma]*), tidy-tips (*Layia platyglossa*), and *Muilla maritima*.

The bay checkerspot's life cycle is tied to host plant biology. Host plants germinate from early October to late December and senesce (dry up and die) from early April to mid May. Most of the active parts of the bay checkerspot life cycle occur during this time. Adults emerge from pupae in early spring, feed on nectar, and mate and lay eggs during a flight season that typically lasts for 4 to 6 weeks from late February to early May. Eggs hatch, and tiny pre-diapause larvae feed for about 2 to 3 weeks and before entering diapause in mid to late spring. Post-diapause larvae emerge after winter rains, stimulated by germination of dwarf plantain, and feed and bask until they are large enough to pupate and emerge as adults.

Studies of bay checkerspots have described its distribution as an example of a metapopulation (Ehrlich *et al.* 1975, Harrison *et al.* 1988). Larvae that diapause (spend a period of dormancy under rocks and deep in soil cracks) for more than one year may be responsible for pseudo-extinctions, since diapausing larvae are essentially undetectable in practical surveys. Because of pseudo-extinction and metapopulation dynamics, even sites that in some years apparently lack the bay checkerspot can be important to species survival and recovery.

The bay checkerspot formerly occurred around San Francisco Bay, from Twin Peaks and San Bruno Mountain (west of the Bay) and Contra Costa County (east of the Bay) south through Santa Clara County. The range of the bay checkerspot is now reduced to patchy distribution in Santa Clara and San Mateo counties. Population trends for the bay checkerspot have generally

been downward in the last decade. Regionally, many populations are currently at historic lows. All areas now or recently inhabited by the bay checkerspot are island-like patches of suitable habitat isolated by intervening unsuitable habitat and urban development. The exact distribution of the butterfly varies through time: sites that are unoccupied one year may be occupied the next, and vice versa. The Service considers any site with appropriate habitat in the vicinity of the historic range of the bay checkerspot to be potentially occupied (Service 1998). The butterfly currently occupies less than 12,000 acres (5,000 ha). Most individuals of the species live only a single year, with high fecundity, high mortality, and sensitivity to weather and other ecological conditions. Large population swings are common; fluctuations of more than 100-fold have been observed. These fluctuations are not always in synchrony among populations at different sites.

Primary reasons for the decline of the bay checkerspot are habitat degradation and loss, caused by non-native plants displacing or reducing native food plants, and by urban and suburban development. The extirpation of several populations has been well documented (Murphy and Weiss 1988a). Several currently proposed or contemplated projects would affect serpentine grassland habitat in the range of the bay checkerspot. Direct strikes and turbulence due to vehicles driving on public roads cause an unknown amount of mortality and injury to bay checkerspots annually. Sizeable and vitally important areas of bay checkerspot habitat lie within the limits of the rapidly growing Santa Clara County, particularly the City of San Jose. The California Court of Appeals recently ruled, in response to a citizens' suit, that San Jose's zoning need not be consistent with its General Plan (San Jose Mercury News, May 10, 1997, p. 2B). The City, therefore, may be limited in its ability to guide growth and development in environmentally sensitive areas.

Grasslands which are grazed at moderate levels (particularly in winter and spring) may favor the bay checkerspot by favoring their native food plants and reducing nonnative plants. The final rule to list the bay checkerspot as a threatened species discussed the role of livestock overgrazing plus drought in the extinction of several populations (Service 1987). While overstocking may adversely affect the species, sustainable grazing practices normally seem to be compatible with the maintenance of bay checkerspot populations. In some parts of its range, grazing is used as a habitat management tool (Thomas Reid Associates and Murphy 1987, Murphy 1988, Weiss 1996). Grazing has been used to manage grasslands for the bay checkerspot (Huenneke *et al.* 1990, Weiss 1999). Grazing, however, may adversely affect some plant species of serpentine grasslands and can damage wetlands (Launer and Murphy 1994).

Invasion of native grasslands by non-native species is widely seen as one of the major causes of bay checkerspot decline. For example, non-native grass growth in the Silver Creek core recovery area has been observed to choke out dwarf plantain (R. White, pers. comm., 1997; A. Launer, pers. comm., 1997; S. Weiss, pers. comm.; 1997, D. Murphy, pers. comm. 1997; as cited in Service 1998). The negative impact of invasive plants on serpentine habitats is increased by fertilization (possibly including nitrogen deposition from air pollution), watering or irrigation, and frequency of introduction of seeds or other propagules (Huenneke *et al.* 1990, Thomas Reid Associates and Murphy 1992, Weiss 1999). Experimental evidence from serpentine grasslands

in San Mateo County indicates that increased levels of nitrogen and other nutrients allow invasion and dominance of non-native annual grasses, causing suppression of native forbs including dwarf plantain.

Use of pesticides, including herbicides, in or near bay checkerspot habitat may affect certain populations. Populations adjacent to development or downwind of areas of heavy pesticide use are most likely to be at risk from pesticide drift. Drift or direct application of herbicides may damage bay checkerspot host plants.

The bay checkerspot's Recovery Plan identifies five known core areas of habitat, four of which occur in Santa Clara County. The Service considers these four core areas to provide a population reservoir critical to the survival of the Santa Clara County metapopulation. Core areas are moderate to large areas of suitable habitat that support persistent bay checkerspot populations. The pattern of occupancy by the bay checkerspot suggests that core populations provide migrants to colonize unoccupied habitat. The Santa Clara core areas are arrayed along Coyote Ridge between the cities of San Jose and Morgan Hill, which has extensive areas of serpentine soils and excellent habitat for the butterfly. The ridge is mostly in private ownership and is largely used as grazing land. The four core areas along Coyote Ridge are separated by discontinuities in the serpentine soils and unsuitable vegetation. Tulare Hill supports resident or intermittent populations of the butterfly and is probably dependent on the health of populations on Coyote Ridge.

Currently little serpentine habitat is set aside to protect the bay checkerspot and other serpentine species. A 128-acre (51.7 ha) private bay checkerspot preserve dedicated by Shea Homes is located in the Silver Creek core area, as is the proposed Ranch on Silver Creek development, a 70-acre preserve proposed by William Lyon Homes (former Presley Homes), and the proposed Ryland Homes Silver Ridge development and private open space. Waste Management Inc. leases a 267-acre (108 ha) reserve on behalf of the Kirby Conservation Trust in the Kirby core area. Serpentine habitat exists in Santa Clara County Parks, Santa Teresa Parks, and other public lands. These lands are protected from urban development but are not managed specifically to protect or enhance serpentine habitat. Santa Teresa Parks specifically forbid grazing on their lands as a land management tool (Weiss *in litt.* 2000). Calpine Corporation placed 131 acres of serpentine habitat in a conservation easement to compensate for nitrogen impacts to serpentine soils, 116 acres on Tulare Hill and 15 acres on Coyote Ridge. The preserves will be managed for the bay checkerspot and serpentine plants in perpetuity.

Bay Checkerspot Critical Habitat

Critical habitat for the bay checkerspot was designated on April 30, 2001, (66 **FR** 21449, Service 2001a). Critical habitat identifies specific areas that are essential to the conservation of a listed species and that may require special management considerations or protection. Areas that do not currently contain the habitat components necessary for the primary biological needs of a species but are likely to develop them in the future may be essential to species conservation and may be designated as critical habitat.

The primary constituent elements for the bay checkerspot are those habitat components that are essential for the primary biological needs of foraging, sheltering, breeding, maturation, and dispersal. The primary constituent elements are found--or could develop--in areas that support or could support grasslands with stands of dwarf plantain, or that provide dispersal corridors between such areas.

Serpentine soils indicate the potential to support the primary constituent elements. Larger areas of habitat are generally capable of supporting larger and more persistent populations of the bay checkerspot. Topographic diversity provides opportunities for early season warmth, as well as cool north- and east-facing slopes that are a refuge for the species during droughts. Bay checkerspot larvae develop more rapidly when they can bask in sunlight that penetrates short-stature grassland vegetation. Adults use warm exposures for basking and find early season nectar plants on warm south- and west-facing slopes. Soil structure with stable holes or cracks and surface rocks or rock outcrops provide cover and shelter for larvae seeking diapause sites. Appropriate vegetation provides cover for larvae, pupae and adults, egg-laying stimuli and sites for females, as well as adequate bare ground for larvae to be able to crawl efficiently in search of foraging, basking, diapause, or pupation sites. Moderate grazing is normally compatible with habitat for the bay checkerspot, since grazing can reduce non-native plant density on serpentine soils. Stands of foodplants including nectar plants are important in the butterfly's life cycle. Adequate native pollinators to sustain populations of owl clover and nectar species are also primary constituent elements of the ecosystem that supports the bay checkerspot. There is evidence that bay checkerspot adults sometimes fly considerable distances during drought conditions to draw water or solutes from moist soils around wetlands (Launer et al. 1993). Potentially suitable wetland areas within critical habitat should be protected at least until the significance of this phenomenon is better understood. Buffer zones may be needed to protect bay checkerspot critical habitat from off-site effects, such as runoff, erosion, spread of non-native plants, intrusion by people, vehicles, or domestic animals, and drift of applied pesticides, water, or fertilizers.

In many areas, occupancy is unknown. Clean air, vegetation, and soil free of pesticides, fertilizers, and other chemicals in concentrations that may adversely affect the butterfly or its ecosystem, and clean water free of chemicals in concentrations that may adversely affect the butterfly, also are primary constituent elements. Existing features and structures within the critical habitat boundary, such as buildings, roads, canals, railroads, large water bodies, lawns, landscaped areas and other features not currently containing or likely to develop these habitat components are not considered habitat. Dispersal is a crucial function for a species with metapopulation dynamics like the bay checkerspot. Therefore, we included corridor areas that allow movement between populations. Not all areas within the designated critical habitat areas are currently occupied by the bay checkerspot. The District will conduct SMP work in the following critical habitat units:

Communications Hill Unit: Communications Hill and adjacent hilltops in south-central San Jose are outcroppings of serpentine rock with grasslands capable of supporting the bay checkerspot.

This unit covers 179 ha (443 ac) of mostly undeveloped land. The bay checkerspot has been documented on Communications Hill in the past. Whether the unit is currently occupied is not known. This unit likely also functions as a “stepping stone” for bay checkerspot dispersal. The unit is surrounded by Curtner Avenue, Almaden Expressway, Hillsdale Avenue, and Monterey Road, and lies 3 km (2 mi) west of the Silver Creek unit.

Kirby Unit: The Kirby unit includes 7,053 acres (2,854 hectares). The Kirby unit is the southernmost of four critical habitat units corresponding to the four core recovery areas along Coyote Ridge and runs along this ridge east of Highway 101 and Coyote Creek from Metcalf Canyon south to Anderson Lake. The northern boundary of the Kirby unit abuts the Metcalf unit. The northwest tip of the Kirby unit also connects to the Tulare Hill Corridor critical habitat unit. This unit regularly supports the largest or second-largest bay checkerspot population and contains several hundred acres of diverse serpentine grassland habitat, nectaring areas, seasonal wetlands, dispersal areas, and some areas of lower or unknown habitat potential. Lands of the Santa Clara Valley Water District and a 267-acre bay checkerspot reserve leased by Waste Management Inc. also fall within the unit (Service 1998).

Metcalf Unit: This unit includes 1,356 ha (3,351 ac) east of Highway 101, south of Silver Creek Valley Road, north of Metcalf Canyon, and west of Silver Creek. The unit contains one of the four largest habitat areas and three largest current population centers for the bay checkerspot (Service 1998). Hundreds of acres of serpentine soils, and thousands of bay checkerspot butterflies, occur within the unit. Protection of the area is of the highest priority for bay checkerspot conservation (Service 1998). This unit adjoins the Kirby unit to the south, San Felipe unit to the east, Silver Creek Hills unit to the north, and Tulare Hill Corridor unit to the west, and provides crucial habitat connectivity for bay checkerspot dispersal among these areas. Lands of Santa Clara Valley Water District fall within the unit.

San Vicente-Calero Unit: This unit contains 759 ha (1,875 ac) within and to the west of Calero County Park and supports a known population of the bay checkerspot in a large area of good-quality habitat. Other areas within the unit that are suitable habitat have not been surveyed. The unit is also within bay checkerspot dispersal distance of the Santa Teresa Hills unit, which is capable of supporting a large bay checkerspot population, and the Kalana Hills unit. The unit is south of McKean Road and east of the town of New Almaden, Almaden Road, and Alamos Creek.

Santa Teresa Hills Unit: This unit includes 1,821 ha (4,500 ac) in Santa Clara County with extensive serpentine soils. Portions of the Santa Teresa Hills are known to support the bay checkerspot now and have supported the species in the past. The Santa Teresa Hills could support a significant population of bay checkerspots. This unit has the potential to provide a fifth substantial population to the Santa Clara County metapopulation. The unit lies north of Bailey Avenue, McKean Road, and Almaden Road, south of developed areas of the city of Santa Clara, and west of Santa Teresa Boulevard. The unit abuts the Tulare Hill Corridor unit.

Tulare Hill Corridor Unit: The Tulare Hill Corridor unit, 876 acres (355 hectares), connects the Coyote Ridge and Santa Teresa Critical Habitat units. Tulare Hill is a prominent serpentine hill in the middle of the Santa Clara Valley west of Highway 101. The bay checkerspot currently occupies extensive habitat on the hill. The hill is essential both as a population center and as a stepping-stone for butterfly dispersal across the Santa Clara Valley. Migrant butterflies from either Santa Teresa Hills or Coyote Ridge may settle on Tulare Hill, contributing individuals and genetic diversity to the population there.

Santa Clara Valley Dudleya

The Santa Clara Valley dudleya (*Dudleya setchellii*) was federally listed as endangered in 1995 (60 **FR** 6671, Service 1995). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area* (Service 1998). The dudleya is a low-growing perennial of the stonecrop family (Crassulaceae) with fleshy, glabrous (hairless) leaves. The oblong to triangular, slightly glaucous (covered with a whitish or bluish waxy or powdery film) leaves are 3 to 8 cm (1 to 3 in.) long and 7 to 15 mm (0.3 to 0.6 in.) wide. Two or three flowering stems ascend to heights of 5 to 20 cm (2 to 8 in.) in mid to late spring. The pale yellow petals are 8 to 13 mm (0.3 to 0.5 in.) long (Hickman 1993).

The dudleya is restricted to rocky outcrops within serpentine grasslands between 120 and 300 m (390 to 990 feet) in Santa Clara County (Hickman 1993). The roots of *Dudleya setchellii* are at least 15 cm (6 in.) long and often extend into rock crevices of the serpentine outcrops (McCarten 1993). The rock outcrops themselves have very little vegetative cover (McCarten 1993).

The dudleya produces wind-dispersed seeds (McCarten 1993). The species also reproduces vegetatively by forming rosettes that can separate from the parent plant or remain attached. Individual plants may live for approximately 10 years. McCarten studied demography of the dudleya at Kirby Canyon Landfill. He found seedling germination was high in wet years, but seedling survivorship was often low in both natural and created habitats. Seedling survival was generally less than 5 percent and may be less than 1 percent after the first year. The highest survival rates observed were on east- and north-facing slopes. The primary cause of low survival may be the limited number of rock crevices with enough soil to provide the necessary nutrient and moisture conditions (Service 1998).

The dudleya is found only in the Coyote Valley area, from San Jose south about 30 km (20 mi.) to San Martin (McCarten 1993) in Santa Clara County (Skinner and Pavlik 1994). Twenty occurrences are currently documented at the CNDDDB.

The species is threatened by development, landfill activities, unauthorized dumping, quarry expansion, and off-road vehicles. Sixteen of the 20 known occurrences are partially or wholly on private land, and most are subject to various levels of threat from development (CNDDDB 1996, CDFG 1997). The northernmost locations in southeastern San Jose and the southernmost locations in the area around Morgan Hill, approximately 27 km (17 mi.) southeast of San Jose, are at greatest risk (McCarten 1993).

In addition, grazing (McCarten 1993, K. Freas, *in litt.*, 1993, D. Mayall, *in litt.*, 1998 as cited in Service 1998) and collecting (Service 1995) may threaten *Dudleya setchellii*. Grazing occurs on much of the grassland where the dudleya is located (McCarten 1993) and may result in reduced vigor or death of mature dudleya individuals and the failure of seedling establishment (K. Freas, *in litt.*, 1993). Unrestricted collecting for scientific or horticultural purposes or excessive visits by individuals interested in seeing rare plants could threaten the dudleya. Due to the slow growth rate of this species and the rarity and desirability of large succulents, mature plants found in the wild are particularly susceptible to collection (Service 1995).

Metcalf Canyon Jewelflower

The Metcalf Canyon jewelflower (*Streptanthus albidus* ssp. *albidus*) was federally listed as endangered in 1995 (60 **FR** 6671, Service 1995). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area* (Service 1998). The jewelflower is an annual herb of the mustard family (Brassicaceae) that reaches up to 1 m (3 ft.) in height. It has bristly hairs at the base and pale green, strongly glaucous stems and leaves. The flowers are borne in leafless terminal racemes (unbranched clusters or inflorescences of stalked flowers that open from bottom to top).

The jewelflower flowers from April to June (Kruckeberg 1977). No detailed data on its reproductive biology or demography are available. Nine populations totaling approximately 20,000 to 25,000 plants have been recorded (McCarten 1992b). The jewelflower is endemic to serpentine outcrops with little soil development within a matrix of mostly native serpentine grassland. The species also has been seen on roadcuts through serpentine substrate. It grows between 60 and 365 m (200 to 1,200 feet) in elevation (McCarten 1992b). The jewelflower grows in areas with other rare species including the bay checkerspot and other plants native to serpentine soils in Santa Clara County.

The jewelflower always has been rare. The known historical distribution is nearly as restricted as its current distribution. It is found only in the Coyote Valley area of Santa Clara Valley, primarily on the east side of the valley. It can be locally abundant, but its range is limited, extending less than 30 km (20 mi.) from San Jose south to Anderson Lake, which lies northeast of Morgan Hill in Santa Clara County. The serpentine outcrops on which the jewelflower occurs are patchily distributed and comprise only a small percentage of the area within its range (McCarten 1992b). Fourteen occurrences are listed in the CNDDDB, with nine occurrences more recently documented and known to be extant (CNDDDB 1996). Because of genetic differences among populations, all populations of the jewelflower are valuable genetic resources (Mayer *et al.* 1994, M. Mayer, *in litt.*, 1998).

The jewelflower is threatened by urbanization, overgrazing, dumping, and off-road vehicle use. Many of the extant populations are in areas being rapidly urbanized (CNDDDB 1996). All nine populations are wholly or partially privately owned. One population is known to have been extirpated by being covered with fill from a housing development, and one was probably

extirpated by the construction of Anderson Dam. Cattle grazing has contributed to reduced population sizes and could result in local extinction of the species within its range. Cattle eat or trample individual plants before they mature and set seed (K. Freas, *in litt.*, 1993). Grazing threatens one population in southeast San Jose and populations in the Metcalf Canyon area (CNDDDB 1996). Road maintenance or construction threaten populations that occur on roadcuts (McCarten 1992b, Service, *in litt.*, 1995, D. Mayall, *in litt.*, 1996 as cited in Service 1998). One population is adjacent to an active quarry and could be threatened by activities associated with its operations (CNDDDB 1996).

Coyote Ceanothus

The Coyote ceanothus (*Ceanothus ferrisiae*) was federally listed as endangered in 1995 (60 **FR** 6671, Service 1995). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area* (Service 1998). Coyote ceanothus is an erect evergreen shrub of the buckthorn family (Rhamnaceae) that grows 1 to 2 m (3 to 6 feet) high, with long stiff divergent branches. Its round leaves are dark green and hairless on the upper surface and lighter green with minute hairs below. The small white flowers are borne in clusters 1.3 to 2.5 cm (0.5 to 1.0 in.) long (McMinn 1933). Coyote ceanothus grows on dry slopes in serpentine chaparral and valley and foothill grassland below 300 m (about 1,000 feet) in elevation (Munz and Keck 1959, Hickman 1993, CNDDDB 1996).

Coyote ceanothus is known from only three locations: Anderson Dam, Kirby Canyon and Llagas Avenue north of Morgan Hill. Prior to 1993, all of the populations were composed of mature and senescent individuals (large plants with many dead branches) (Freas *in litt.* 1993). The population in Kirby Canyon, the smallest of the three, burned during the summer of 1992. The following spring approximately 2,000 seedlings were observed (Service 1998). These seedlings were fenced to protect them from grazing until the plants were established, and 100 plants were individually caged. One year later survivorship of the caged seedlings was good (Service 1998). Freas conducted germination trials using various heat and disturbance treatments (Freas *in litt.*, 1993). Her results suggest that Coyote ceanothus seeds do not require fire for germination. Despite the results of the germination trials, the only seedlings observed in nature were following a fire in Kirby Canyon (Service 1998).

All known locations of the Coyote ceanothus are within 6 km (4 mi.) of each other in Santa Clara County. Fewer than 6,000 plants are known to exist (Service 1995). The largest population, consisting of approximately 5,000 plants, occurs near Anderson Dam, partially on Santa Clara County Park property and partially on private property (Corelli 1991). Prior to 1993, Freas (*in litt.*, 1993) monitored the three populations of Coyote ceanothus. She found no evidence of seedling recruitment and observed that all of the populations were composed of mature and senescent individuals (large plants with many dead branches).

The existing populations of Coyote ceanothus are threatened by residential and recreational development, unauthorized dumping, landfill activities, lack of natural recruitment (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service 1995), altered fire regimes (C. Schmidt, *in litt.*, 1996, 1998), grazing

(CNDDDB 1996) and stochastic events (involving random or chance processes) (K. Freas, *in litt.*, 1993). The Kirby Canyon population which occurs 3.2 km (2 mi.) west of Anderson Dam is on property leased and managed by Waste Management of California, Inc. This population is threatened by cattle grazing and dumping (CNDDDB 1996). The third population (Llagas Avenue north of Morgan Hill), consisting of approximately 500 plants, occurs on private land (Corelli 1991, CNDDDB 1996). Although Coyote ceanothus still occurs at the site, a portion of the occurrence had been developed as of April 1997. When the site was last visited, the plants seemed to be rather senescent and all of the same age class (CDFG 1997).

Tiburon paintbrush

Tiburon paintbrush (*Castilleja affinis* ssp. *neglecta*) (paintbrush) was federally listed as endangered in 1995 (60 **FR** 6671, Service 1995). A detailed account of the taxonomy, ecology, and biology of the species is presented in the *Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area* (Service 1998). The paintbrush is a semi-woody perennial of the snapdragon family (Scrophulariaceae), with erect, branched stems 30 to 60 cm (1 to 2 ft.) tall and a sparse covering of soft, spreading hairs (Munz and Keck 1959). The lance-shaped leaves are 20 to 40 mm (0.8 to 1.6 in.) long and have 0 to 5 lobes (Hickman 1993). The conspicuous floral bracts are yellowish and sometimes red-tipped; the flowers are yellow to red and 18 to 20 mm (0.7 to 0.8 in.) long. The paintbrush is a root parasite on other flowering plant species. The primary advantage of the parasitic attachment in *Castilleja* and related plants is reportedly an increased water and mineral supply. Though the parasitic relationship is not obligate (hemiparasitic), benefits to species of *Castilleja* from the parasitic habit are manifested in increased vigor with more branching, greater height, and earlier flowering (Service 1998).

Tiburon paintbrush occurs in serpentine bunchgrass communities (Fiedler and Leidy 1987, California Natural Diversity Data Base 1996) at elevations between about 75 and 400 meters (250 and 1,300 feet) (California Natural Diversity Data Base 1996). It flowers from April to June (Munz and Keck 1959). Lawrence Heckard (*in litt.*, 1989) postulated that the yellow flowers were largely bee-pollinated. Seeds are shed in June and July, and the species dies back to its woody base in July and August. New growth from the woody base begins in December or January. Seeds may remain dormant in the soil for several years. Seed germination occurs in January or February and seems to be induced by leaching and low temperatures (Martin 1989).

Tiburon paintbrush has never been widespread. Three of the eight populations occur on the Tiburon Peninsula in Marin County, one occurs in Napa County, and two are in Santa Clara County. Populations are small, ranging from fewer than 20 plants at the Kirby Canyon site (CNDDDB 1996) to approximately 600 plants at Ring Mountain Preserve on the Tiburon Peninsula (Hunter 1989). The northern Kirby Canyon paintbrush population is on a preserve for bay checkerspot butterfly conservation (N. McCarten, *in litt.*, 1998). The reserve is a 107-ha (267-acre) area set aside as mitigation for the development of the Kirby Canyon Landfill (Murphy 1988, Thomas Reid Associates and Murphy 1992). The other population, discovered following the publication of the Recovery Plan for serpentine species, is located near Pigeon Point north of Anderson Dam. Populations of Tiburon paintbrush in Santa Clara County occur

on private land. Cattle grazing has been reported to threaten some occurrences of the paintbrush (Hunter 1989), but the exact effect is unknown. The northern Santa Clara County population consists of 13 plants and is subject to low levels of grazing (R. Bittman, pers. comm., 1993). Exact grazing levels at the Anderson Dam property are unknown.

Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects to California red-legged frog

Direct effects include the potential for harassment, injury, and mortality of all red-legged frog life stages during bank protection, sediment removal, vegetation management, and access road repair. Red-legged frogs will be harmed (both directly and indirectly) from habitat impacts during bank protection, sediment removal, vegetation management, and access road repair. Sediment removal typically occurs in areas where the stream has begun to succeed to a state of ecological and geomorphic stability. Channels in later successional stages, with diverse aquatic and vegetative habitats provide superior habitat for red-legged frogs than uniform trapezoidal flood-control channels that have been cleared of pools and vegetation. Sediment removal and vegetation management removes emergent and riparian vegetation that provide cover and egg mass attachment sites, and eliminates pools containing cool water. Sediment removal downstream of the Almaden mine may mobilize mercury-contaminated sediment in the Alamitos Creek watershed, causing indirect harm to red-legged frogs by exposing them to increased concentrations of mercury.

Installation of hardscape will preclude formation of riparian and emergent plant community at bank stabilization sites. At least half of all bank stabilization will utilize soft structures which incorporate riparian or wetland vegetation in their designs. While these designs minimize some of the impact of these structures to the stream, they are still an effort to control the natural processes of a dynamic stream, impacting the ecosystem. Also, these sites will be designed to reduce streambank erosions rather than create habitat for the red-legged frog. The extent to which these “softscape” structures will support red-legged frog habitat is not known. Ground squirrel control will indirectly affect the red-legged frog. Reduced ground squirrel populations will result in reduced numbers of ground squirrel burrows near streams, eliminating red-legged frog estivation habitat.

Red-legged frogs found during pre-construction surveys will be harassed when they are moved from work areas to suitable habitat. Red-legged frogs that are moved may be subjected to physiological stress and may be disoriented and attempt to return to the work site. They may be exposed to an increased stress level and may expose themselves to predators. Relocating red-legged frogs during the breeding season could cause reproductive failures as a result of stress.

Creating preserves and managing them for the red-legged frog will have a long-term indirect benefit to the species. Purchasing lands for preservation will protect them from development in the future. However, setting aside these high-elevation preserves as the only conservation areas

will improve habitat in the perimeter of the valley but will not directly benefit red-legged frog populations in lowland areas.

Adverse indirect effects include the potential for increased sedimentation downstream from the sediment removal and bank protection activities. Runoff from access roads will carry sediment to the streams. The presence of construction crews on site could result in an increase in on-site trash and could attract potential predators, such as skunks and racoons.

Normal construction activities are likely to result in direct effects to red-legged frogs through spills and intrusion into habitat areas by crews and equipment. Petrochemicals, soaps or solvents that are spilled or may be leaking from vehicles could kill red-legged frogs during all life stages. Sediment washing downstream after storm events could suffocate embryos and tadpoles. Frogs displaced by construction or other disturbance may be required to compete for food and living space with animals in adjacent areas.

Effects to Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and California Clapper Rail

Direct effects to the harvest mouse and clapper rail will include harassment, injury, harm, and mortality during bank protection, sediment removal, vegetation management. Although the District will survey for these species in potential habitat prior to starting work, the secretive nature of these species provides a high likelihood that they may not be found during surveys. Clapper rails will be harassed by equipment operating in their habitat and when chased away by biologists. Although clapper rails can become habituated to regular human contact, District facilities have no public access; therefore clapper rails at these sites are unlikely to be habituated to human presence. Chasing them and operating heavy equipment in their presence is likely to be highly stressful.

Removing shallow mudflats will harm the clapper rail by eliminating foraging habitat. Removing sediment and vegetation from tidal channels will remove foraging and cover habitat for both the harvest mouse and clapper rail. Sediment removal to maintain a wide flood control channel is expected to prevent the formation of stable, sinuous tidal channels and colonization of vegetative cover suitable for nesting and cover. Leaks and spills of fuels, lubricants, and other fluids from heavy equipment could kill invertebrates and small vertebrates, which the clapper rail depends on for food. A total of 29 acres of tidal wetlands are expected to be affected by sediment removal and 1 acre of tidal wetlands is expected to be affected by vegetation management over the course of the 10-year permit. The District estimates approximately 11.0 acres of this area contains clapper rail habitat.

Harvest mice are expected to be crushed and harassed by heavy equipment during sediment removal and vegetation activities. Clearing tidal channels will prevent succession of stable tidal channels and tidal marsh terraces, reducing the formation of suitable habitat for the harvest mouse in the action area.

The clapper rail and harvest mouse are likely to benefit from the restoration of Pond A4 to tidal action. However, design work will not begin until 2006, and it will take many years to provide tidal marsh habitat for these species.

Effects to Western Snowy Plover

Nesting snowy plover adults, eggs and chicks are likely to be crushed by heavy equipment conducting maintenance on levees. Motorized vehicles may cause adult plovers to abandon their nests. Plover adults and chicks may use tire tracks for loafing, increasing their chances for mortality. Adult plovers will be harassed by work crews and equipment during vegetation removal and levee maintenance, which will interfere with normal feeding and breeding activities. Dredging channels and installing hardscape on levees adjacent to plover habitat will affect plovers indirectly by rendering the areas unsuitable for plover nesting. Hardscape will lead to plover predation indirectly by creating desirable habitat for plover predators such as rats and skunks.

Effects to Least Bell's Vireo

Only four vireos have been sighted in the Pajaro River basin since 1997, so direct effects to individual birds are unlikely. However, these birds may be important because they are the northernmost occurrence of the species in several decades. Least Bell's vireos nesting in the Pajaro River basin could suffer direct mortality and harm during vegetation removal activities. The SMP is likely to have both positive and negative indirect effects on the vireo. Arundo removal will allow native riparian vegetation to grow along Llagas Creek and the Pajaro River, which will benefit the vireo. The District has proposed to conduct vegetation management only upstream of Highway 152; however, there is no guarantee that the vireo will not attempt to colonize habitat in this area. Sediment removal in the Pajaro basin will prevent succession of riparian habitat, which will affect the vireo indirectly. Out-of-channel vegetation removal in Pajaro basin will create open areas suitable for brown-headed cowbirds, which are likely present in the basin due to extensive agricultural activity. Promoting cowbird habitat will affect vireos indirectly.

Continual vegetation clearing could have other indirect effects on the vireo. Fragmentation of riparian habitat can reduce or extirpate populations of large predators such as bobcats, which results in an increase in the numbers of medium-sized carnivores such as raccoons, skunks, and opossums, all of which prey on vireo nests.

Effects to Bay Checkerspot and Bay Checkerspot Critical Habitat

The SMP will cause both direct and indirect effects to the bay checkerspot, partially in the form of mortality but primarily in the form of harm due to habitat disturbance. Mowing and disking of channel banks and uplands on serpentine soils, both within and outside of critical habitat units, will kill butterfly larvae and remove larval host plants and adult nectar plants. Disking and mowing also have a long-term beneficial effect by controlling nonnative weeds that can

outcompete the plants necessary for the bay checkerspot's survival. The District considers some serpentine areas to be unsuitable for the bay checkerspot and plans to survey potential habitat. Stream maintenance work on serpentine soils in unsurveyed areas may impact bay checkerspots or dwarf plantain.

Pesticides, including herbicides, in or near serpentine habitat may affect the bay checkerspot. Butterfly populations adjacent to levees or downwind of areas of heavy pesticide use are most likely to be at risk from pesticide drift. Drift or direct application of herbicides may damage bay checkerspot host plants. The District will survey all serpentine habitat areas for the bay checkerspot host plant prior to herbicide use. No herbicides will be directly on host plant populations. Therefore, drift is the most likely effect to the bay checkerspot.

Effects to Dudleya, Jewelflower, Ceanothus, and Paintbrush

Herbicides, disking, and mowing are likely to have direct effects on the listed serpentine plants. Since the dudleya primarily occupies rock outcrops, it is less likely than the other plant species. However, some District facilities are adjacent to serpentine rock outcrops (District 2001). Grading and weeding to maintain access roads may create favorable conditions for the jewelflower to colonize new areas, which could later be destroyed by subsequent maintenance actions. District staff will survey all serpentine areas for special-status plants. All special-status plants found during surveys will be mapped and avoided. No known populations of ceanothus or paintbrush occur where SMP work will occur; therefore, effects to these species are unlikely.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act.

California Red-legged Frog

Much of the open space remaining within eastern Santa Clara County is characterized by steep slopes and undulating ridge tops. The continued development of ridge tops will result in the loss of not only red-legged frog breeding and foraging habitat, but the loss of dispersal corridors across ridges, further isolating remaining red-legged frogs in this area. Some streams may be channelized or moved to provide space for homes or crop production. Some hills in this area are severely overgrazed, which can be detrimental to upland and aquatic habitat essential for red-legged frog survival.

Red-legged frog populations within the action area are subject to increasing encroachment of urban and suburban development around San Jose and elsewhere in Santa Clara County. Impacts by other projects involving wetland fill or waters subject to Corps jurisdiction will be addressed in future section 7 consultations. However, impacts to the red-legged frog's upland

habitats often go unaddressed, as do direct impacts to wetland habitats that lack a detectable population of the red-legged frog. Nevertheless, these areas function as dispersal or occasional refugial habitat or support a low-level presence of the species. The City of San Jose has a nominal standard of 100-foot riparian setbacks for all construction activities. However, this standard, even if aggressively applied, is inadequate to protect the red-legged frog when otherwise surrounded by development. Urban and suburban development of upland habitats will reduce red-legged frog populations by preventing adults and juveniles from reaching their breeding ponds or summer refuges, and by fragmenting populations into isolated habitat remnants. Many such remnants will not maintain viable populations of the species without broad connection to adjacent habitats, because their resident populations are too small and are subject to extirpation. Chance environmental events such as drought, random population fluctuations, or genetic effects can eliminate these population which can no longer be “rescued” or re-colonized by dispersing frogs immigrating from other locations.

Red-legged frogs also will continue to experience other cumulative effects. Predation and competition from introduced species such as bullfrogs, crayfish, and various fish are an ongoing problem for the red-legged frog in the action area. We expect urban and suburban development to favor these introduced species by increasing runoff volumes, creating perennial flows, and increasing the area of disturbed land. We expect detrimental aquatic contaminants to increase with increased urban and suburban development. Runoff from roads, parking lots, driveways, and landscaped areas carries petroleum-derived residues, fertilizers, pesticides, and other contaminants toxic to frogs, especially to their egg and tadpole stages, impairing reproduction, survival, and development.

A number of development projects are now underway or reasonably certain to take place that are likely to adversely affect red-legged frog populations within San Jose and Santa Clara County. Effects are expected to include restricting upland habitat and dispersal corridors, altering wetland hydrology and chemistry, introducing competitive and predatory species, and inducing growth and development in additional areas that are currently less developed.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and California Clapper Rail

One of the most serious cumulative effects on the harvest mouse and clapper rail has been the degradation of diked wetlands, typically by the elimination of wetland vegetation by grazing, discing, grubbing, plowing, and/or the elimination of appropriate hydrologic conditions by installing drains, ditches, and pumps. The extensive conversion of South Bay salt marshes to brackish and freshwater habitat also has severely reduced available tidal habitat for these species.

Other cumulative effects to the harvest mouse and clapper rail include chemical contamination and urban encroachment. Chemical contamination from point and non-point discharges adversely affect survival rates and reproductive success of the harvest mouse and clapper rail. Chemical runoff contaminated with sediment, nutrients, and pesticides pollutes the sloughs and wetlands of the South Bay. Environmental contaminants may affect the health and vigor of

clapper rails directly through toxic effects to individuals or indirectly through effects to organisms upon which the rail depends. Known contaminants in the San Francisco Estuary include mercury, selenium, PCBs, and petroleum hydrocarbons. The potential toxicological effects of long term chronic contaminant exposures can include reproductive impairment, compromised immune function, reduced growth, deformity, and altered behavior. While few adult clapper rail mortalities have been attributed directly to contaminants, mercury has been elevated in tissues of some adults found dead. Reproduction in clapper rails has been documented as poor and contaminants, particularly mercury and perhaps PCBs, are likely the most important contributors (Service unpubl. data).

Urban expansion in South Bay counties has increased rapidly in the 1990s. Most urban developments give little consideration to maintaining adequate distances from tidal marsh habitat to prevent the resultant predation by dogs and cats and increased populations of skunks, rats, and raccoons. Approval of urban developments without maintaining adequate upland habitat adjacent to wetlands increases mortality rates and lowers harvest mouse and clapper rail carrying capacities in affected areas. Urban development creates favorable conditions for predators of the harvest mouse and clapper rail, particularly raccoons (*Procyon lotor*), skunks (*Mephitis mephitis*), nonnative rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) and cats (*Felis domesticus*). This is exacerbated by predator release programs, which relocate nuisance animals from adjacent urban areas. Hunting intensity and efficiency by raptors on clapper rails also is increased by electric power transmission lines and access to boardwalks, which cross tidal marshes and provide otherwise-limited hunting perches.

Western Snowy Plover

Cumulative effects to the snowy plover are caused primarily by urban growth in the Bay area and on the coast. Increases in urbanized landscape will continue to contribute to high-intensity flows in streams in the Santa Clara basin, which will potentially compromise levee strength surrounding Pond A8, due to increased velocities in Guadalupe River and Alviso Slough. Many of the channel improvements proposed by this project consist of a hard surface, such as concrete or riprap. This hardscape in the bed and on the banks of a river increases flow velocities, which places downstream levees at greater risk of damage and failure. Construction of seawalls, recreational facilities, and trails cause direct and indirect losses of breeding and wintering habitat. Sand mined in coastal areas causes erosion and loss of habitat. Invasion of European beach grass (*Ammophila arenaria*) has eliminated hundreds of acres of snowy plover habitat on the coast. Restoration of salt ponds to tidal marsh for the benefit of the harvest mouse and clapper rail may have adverse effects on snowy plover populations in the South Bay if protective measures are not incorporated into restoration design (Service 2001).

Least Bell's Vireo

As human populations increased in California, riparian woodlands were cleared for agriculture and inundated when dams were constructed. Flood control projects and channelization of rivers further reduces available least Bell's vireo habitat. The District plans to construct the Upper

Llagas CIP, which will affect flows in Llagas Creek. Flow velocities will increase when the stream is channelized and levees are constructed to keep flows off the floodplain. Higher peak flows and flow velocities will increase and potential for scour of riparian vegetation or sediment bars where riparian vegetation frequently colonizes.

Livestock grazing destroys the choice lower strata of vegetation preferred by the vireo and provides habitat for cowbirds. Highway projects and urban, commercial, and recreational developments continue to encroach on riparian and floodplain habitat. Roads and highways generate noise and pollutants, further reducing the suitability of riparian areas for vireo nesting. Free-roaming and feral domestic predators pose a risk to nesting birds, as do increased densities of scrub jays (*Aphelocoma coerulescens*), racoons, and other predators associated with urban development. The widespread and precipitous decline of the species left small populations in scattered riparian remnants. These conditions make the vireo vulnerable to local and possibly range-wide extinction. Large interpopulation distances reduce the opportunity for dispersal and resultant genetic exchange among populations, heightening the risk of inbreeding (Soule 1980, Conway, 1980, Senner 1980 as cited in Service 1998b). Recovery action 2.12-surveys w/in range.

Bay Checkerspot and Bay Checkerspot Critical Habitat

Likely future non-Federal actions in the project vicinity that will cumulatively affect the bay checkerspot include continuing urban and suburban development in habitat of the species, an unknown but probably relatively small amount of illegal collecting, and adverse effects on habitat of the species from deposition of nitrogen from air pollution. Nitrogen deposition degrades bay checkerspot habitat by fertilizing otherwise infertile serpentine soils, stimulating the growth of invasive non-native plants (Weiss 1999, Huenneke *et al.* 1990, Service 1998). With such fertilization, taller or more aggressive non-natives may crowd out the bay checkerspot's food plants. Depending on the impact of nitrogen deposition, air pollution may come to present an extreme threat to the survival of the bay checkerspot, since several vital populations in Santa Clara county are vulnerable to air pollution effects (Weiss 1999). Finally, we believe that bay checkerspot metapopulations will continue to decline in part because of continuing adjustment to past habitat loss and fragmentation. These past impacts are only gradually becoming fully evident because of time lags inherent in the butterfly's population and metapopulation responses. Because of the tenuous range wide population status and the severity of the ongoing and cumulative effects, we believe that the bay checkerspot cannot tolerate appreciable further erosion of its present baseline population status.

A proposed project to widen and straighten a portion of Metcalf Road in the City of San Jose would impact adjacent serpentine habitats, increase road kills of bay checkerspots, and improve human access to Coyote Ridge and highly significant bay checkerspot habitat: the Kirby, Metcalf, and San Felipe core populations.

Dudleya, Jewelflower, Ceanothus, and Paintbrush

The endangered plants are subject to cumulative effects similar to those described above for the bay checkerspot. However, since animals have stronger protections under the Act than plants, the effects are likely to be more extensive for the plants. All four plant species occur in areas desirable for urban development. Because of this, the plants are losing habitat directly, through conversion of serpentine grasslands and outcrops to residential and associated development. The remaining habitat also is becoming nitrogen-enriched from the resulting increase in smog. An increase in nitrogen can encourage non-native grasses which can effectively shade out dudleya plants, restricting them to the most severe rocky outcrops which support no grasses. The jewelflower, which occurs primarily in serpentine grasslands, could be particularly affected by non-native grasses. The ceanothus and paintbrush may be affected by altered fire regimes that result from encroaching urban boundaries. Fire suppression near the urban-wilderness interface reduces the likelihood of natural regeneration of this species.

Not all projects that impact listed plants or their habitat are reviewed by the Service. For example, at a development project at one of the largest dudleya populations, an unsuccessful attempt was made to move entire dudleya-bearing serpentine rocks to a preserve. The project proponent did not confer with the Service on the most appropriate impact minimization measures for this project (N. McCarten, Jones & Stokes, pers. comm., March 26, 1998). The Service anticipates that the trend of urban expansion will continue to threaten the remaining serpentine grasslands containing listed plant habitat.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the species, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed action and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed implementation of the SMP, including the avoidance and minimization measures proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the red-legged frog, harvest mouse, clapper rail, snowy plover, vireo, bay checkerspot, dudleya, jewelflower, ceanothus, and paintbrush. The program is not likely to destroy or adversely modify designated critical habitat for the bay checkerspot. No critical habitat has been designated for the clapper rail, harvest mouse, dudleya, jewelflower, ceanothus, or paintbrush; therefore, none will be affected. Critical habitat for this red-legged frog has been designated within Santa Clara County; however, this action does not affect that area, and no destruction or adverse modification of that critical habitat is anticipated. No critical habitat has been designated for the snowy plover or the vireo in Santa Clara County; therefore, none will be destroyed or adversely modified.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9(a)(1) of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened fish and wildlife species without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an

extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by impairing behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be implemented by the agency so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, in order for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, and/or (2) fails to retain oversight to ensure compliance with these terms and conditions, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse.

Sections 7(b)(4) and 7(o)(2) of ESA, which refer to terms and conditions and exemptions on taking listed fish and wildlife species, do not apply to listed plant species. However, section 9(a)(2) of the Act prohibits removal, reduction to possession, and malicious damage or destruction of listed plant species on Federal lands and the removal, cutting, digging up, or damaging or destroying such species in knowing violation of any State law or regulation, including State criminal trespass law. Actions funded, authorized or implemented by a Federal agency that could incidentally result in the damage or destruction of such species on Federal lands are not a violation of the Act, provided the Service determines in a biological opinion that the actions are not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the species.

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service expects that incidental take of the red-legged frog, harvest mouse, clapper rail, plover, vireo, and bay checkerspot will be difficult to detect or quantify for several reasons: aquatic nature (red-legged frog), relatively small body size (red-legged frog, harvest mouse, snowy plover, vireo), heavily vegetated habitat (harvest mouse, clapper rail, vireo, bay checkerspot), secretive nature (clapper rail, snowy plover), cryptic coloration (red-legged frog, harvest mouse, clapper rail, snowy plover), masking of losses by seasonal fluctuations in numbers (red-legged frog, harvest mouse, bay checkerspot) or other causes. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the numbers of any of the listed species in this consultation that will be taken as a result of the proposed action, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the project as all individuals in the number of acres of habitat that will become unsuitable for the species as a result of the action. The Service estimates that the following habitats will become unsuitable as a result of the proposed action: 29.3 acres of red-legged frog habitat, 11.0 acres of harvest mouse habitat, 11.0 acres of clapper rail habitat, 5.0 acres of snowy plover habitat, 3.0 acres of vireo habitat, and 5.0 acres of bay checkerspot habitat. In addition, incidental take in the form of

harm, harassment, or killing associated with SMP on these acres of habitat will be exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act for indirect impacts as a result of the management activities described, with the exception of killing of the harvest mouse and clapper rail, and take of any species associated with instream pesticide use. The harvest mouse and clapper rail are fully protected species under State law; therefore take in the form of direct mortality is not be exempted in this biological opinion. The effects of pesticides on listed species are not covered due to the lack of analysis of the effects of these chemicals on listed species.

Effect of the Take

The Service has determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the listed wildlife species in this opinion or result in destruction or adverse modification of critical habitat.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measures are necessary and appropriate to minimize the impact of the SMP on threatened and endangered species:

1. Minimize the potential for direct and indirect mortality, harm, and harassment of the red-legged frog from the SMP.
2. Minimize the potential for direct and indirect mortality, harm, and harassment of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from the SMP.
3. Minimize the potential for direct and indirect mortality, harm, and harassment of the snowy plover from the SMP.
4. Minimize the potential for direct and indirect mortality, harm, and harassment of the least Bell's vireo from the SMP.
5. Minimize the potential for direct and indirect mortality and harm of the bay checkerspot and bay checkerspot critical habitat from the SMP.
6. Minimize the potential for mortality and harassment of the red-legged frog, harvest mouse, clapper rail, snowy plover, and vireo from surveys associated with the SMP.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of ESA, the Corps must comply with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measures described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 1, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:
 - a. The District shall complete the purchase of the red-legged frog preserves within 5 years of the date of this opinion. The District shall not initiate new work in red-legged frog habitat in the sixth year of the permit until the property has been purchased.
 - b. Within one year of the purchase of the red-legged frog preserve lands, the District shall record a Service-approved conservation easement which shall be placed on all on-site and off-site habitats set aside for the protection of red-legged frogs and their habitat in perpetuity. The easement shall include, but not be limited to, provisions and responsibilities of the District, including any future transfers of the easement or fee interest that may be anticipated. The easement shall specify the purposes for which it is established (*i.e.*, measures to minimize impacts to red-legged frogs. The Service shall receive a true copy of the recorded conservation easement within 30 days of its recordation. The easement shall include a list of prohibited activities that are inconsistent with the maintenance of the preserve for the listed species including, but not limited to:
 - (1) Leveling, grading, landscaping, cultivation, or any other alterations of existing topography for any purposes, including the exploration for, or development of, mineral resources;
 - (2) discharge, dumping, burning, or storing of rubbish, garbage, grass clippings, dredge material, household chemicals, or any other wastes within the preserve;
 - (3) killing, removal, alteration, or replacement of any existing native vegetation except in Service-approved prescribed burning situations;
 - (4) activities that may alter the hydrology of the preserve and the associated watersheds, including but not limited to pumping of groundwater, manipulation or blockage of natural drainages, or inappropriate water application or placement of storm water drains;
 - (5) incompatible fire protection activities;
 - (6) use of pesticides, herbicides, or rodenticides on the preserve or within the watershed that can contaminate the preserve; and
 - (7) introduction of any exotic or invasive species, including aquatic species.
 - c. Within one year the acquisition of the preserve, a Management Plan for the red-legged frog preserve areas shall be completed and approved by the Service. This Management Plan shall include, but not be limited to:

- (1) discussions of the management and maintenance in perpetuity of the habitats for the red-legged frog, including documentation that adequate funds exist for monitoring and perpetual management and maintenance;
 - (2) provisions for management and maintenance in perpetuity of upland habitat within the on-site habitat protection area, including discussion of grazing strategies, alien species control, sedimentation, erosion, and controlled burning;
 - (3) a description of the duties to be undertaken by the Preserve Manager;
 - (4) provisions for a monitoring program to be set up and implemented by the Preserve Manager, with an annual monitoring report that addresses endangered species use of protected habitat and the ecological functions of the preserve;
 - (5) a description of adequate fencing and signs to be placed and maintained around the preserve;
 - (6) provisions for removal of trash and debris from the preserve by the Preserve Manager on a bimonthly basis or more frequently, if needed;
 - (7) provisions for an annual written report by the Preserve Manager, with copies sent to the Service, Corps, and CDFG on the status of the red-legged frog within the preserve. The report shall, if necessary, recommend maintenance practices, repairs, *etc.*, (subject to review and approval by the Service) necessary to ensure the preserve continues to function as listed species habitat;
 - (8) development of success criteria for endangered species use of existing habitat and all created features; and
 - (9) development of a contingency plan in the event that management of the habitat protection areas does not meet success criteria.
- d. All proposed trail alignments within the preserve must be approved by the Service.
- e. The District shall not use hardscape bank stabilization in unmodified channels.
- f. Within three years of the date of this opinion, the District shall conduct an inventory of all channel access roads within its jurisdiction and report this inventory to the Service. Included in this report shall be methods to reduce the number of channel access roads and a list of sites where natural channels can be restored.
- g. Amplexing red-legged frogs shall not be disturbed. If amplexing frogs or tadpoles are found at a work site, work shall be postponed until September 15.
- h. No herbicides shall be used in aquatic areas within red-legged frog habitat.
2. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 2, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:

- a. Rather than chasing clapper rails away from sediment removal and vegetation management sites in tidal areas, the District shall cease work at these areas until the rail has left the area of its own volition.
 - b. To reduce the temporal effects of tidal habitat loss, the District shall implement a control program to eliminate the exotic species *Spartina alterniflora*, beginning in 2003, the District shall not conduct any work in tidal channels until the plan has been finalized. Implementation of the Spartina control program shall be completed by 2010.
 - c. Beginning in 2006, the District shall not conduct any work in tidal channels until the design for the restoration of Pond A4 has been completed.
 - d. Prior to restoration, the District shall ensure that adequate harvest mouse habitat exists adjacent to pond A4 to provide source populations for the site. Temporary refuges (partitioned sub-parcels managed as nontidal pickleweed marsh) may be integrated with restoration as necessary.
3. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 3, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:
- a. No work shall be done within 500 feet of a known snowy plover nesting area (including adjacent levees) during the breeding season.
 - b. The District shall not use hardscape in bank stabilization design within 2,000 feet of a known snowy plover breeding site.
4. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 4, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:
- a. Giant reed removal sites shall be revegetated with native vegetation. Revegetation sites may not be cleared during vegetation management activities.
 - b. The District shall not use any hardscape within in unmodified channels in the Pajaro drainage or within 1 mile of Bank stabilization and minor maintenance. They shall consult with the Service on case-by-case basis on access road repair.
 - c. The area of any sediment removal action under bridges in the Pajaro River drainage may not exceed 0.1 acre of stream.
5. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 5, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:
- a. The District shall not apply other chemicals in type or amount that would kill bay checkerspots or impair any of their biological functions, such as feeding or reproduction. Only chemicals known to be harmless to checkerspots may be used. The District shall provide the Service with written documentation that proposed chemicals are nontoxic to bay checkerspots.
 - b. No herbicides shall be used on serpentine soils, whether within designated critical habitat or not.
 - c. The District shall not disturb serpentine rock outcrops with heavy equipment.

- d. If red-legged frog preserves are located within serpentine habitat or bay checkerspot critical habitat, the District shall ensure that all management actions in the preserves are compatible with bay checkerspot conservation and do not have a negative impact on critical habitat constituent elements.
- a. To implement Reasonable and Prudent Measure number 6, the Corps shall ensure the District complies with the following:
 - a. All persons handling red-legged frogs during preconstruction surveys shall be approved by the Service or be under the direct supervision of a Service-approved individual.
 - b. All persons conducting surveys for harvest mouse, clapper rail, snowy plover, or vireo shall be approved by the Service or be under the direct supervision of a Service-approved individual.

The reasonable and prudent measures, with their implementing terms and conditions, are designed to minimize the impact of incidental take on a species that might result from the proposed action. The Service believes that individuals on no more than 29.3 acres of red-legged frog habitat, 11.0 acres of harvest mouse habitat, 11.0 acres of clapper rail habitat, 5.0 acres of snowy plover habitat, 3.0 acres of vireo habitat, and 5.0 acres of bay checkerspot habitat will be incidentally taken. If, during the course of the action, this level of incidental take is exceeded, such incidental take would represent new information requiring review of the reasonable and prudent measures provided. The Federal agency must immediately provide an explanation of the causes of the taking and review with the Service the need for possible modification of the reasonable and prudent measures.

Reporting Requirements

The Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office is to be notified within three working days of the finding of any dead listed wildlife species or any unanticipated harm to the species addressed in this biological opinion. The Service contact person for this is Jan C. Knight, Chief, Endangered Species Division at (916) 414-6620.

The Corps must require the District to report to the Service immediately any information about take or suspected take of listed wildlife species not authorized in this opinion. The Corps must notify the Service within 24 hours of receiving such information. Notification must include the date, time, and location of the incident of the incident or of the finding of a dead or injured animal. The Service contact is the Service's Law Enforcement Division at (916) 414-6660.

Any contractor or employee who during routine operations and maintenance activities inadvertently kills or injures a listed wildlife species must immediately report the incident to their representative. This representative must contact the California Department of Fish and Game immediately. The California Department of Fish and Game contact for immediate assistance is State Dispatch at (916) 445-0045.

The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Regional Office in Portland, Oregon, must be notified immediately if any dead, injured, or sick listed wildlife species is found in or adjacent to

pesticide-treated areas. Cause of death or illness, if known, also should be conveyed to this office. The appropriate contact is Richard Hill at (503) 231-6241.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of ESA directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities that can be implemented to further the purposes of the Act, such as preservation of endangered species habitat, implementation of recovery actions, or development of information and data bases.

3. To reduce sediment transport from undeveloped upland areas, the Service recommends that the District develop a grant program to assist private landowners in improving land and soil management and reducing erosion.
4. The Service recommends that the District select some flood control facilities to return, as closely as possible, to a state of geomorphic stability.
5. The Service recommends that the terms and conditions implemented for the protection of the Bay checkerspot be implemented to protect the listed serpentine plants.
6. The Service recommends that the District conduct a comprehensive rare plant survey on all serpentine soils within their jurisdiction.
7. The Corps and the District should use their authorities to implement recovery for the red-legged frog, clapper rail, harvest mouse, snowy plover, vireo, bay checkerspot, dudleya, jewelflower, ceanothus, and paintbrush.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefitting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION--CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the action outlined in the request. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been maintained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in this opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any operations causing such take must cease pending reinitiation.

Please contact Cecilia Brown or Dan Buford of this office at (916) 414-6625 if you have any questions. For questions regarding wetlands, please contact Mark Littlefield at (916) 414-6580.

Sincerely,

Mr. Calvin C. Fong

43

Cay C. Goude
Acting Field Supervisor

cc:

Santa Clara Valley Water District, San Jose, CA (Attn: Lee Ellis, Project Manager)

PARD, Region 1 Office, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

National Marine Fisheries Service, Santa Rosa, CA (Attn: Maura Eagan)

Regional Water Quality Control Board, Oakland, CA (Attn: Paul Amato)

Regional Water Quality Control Board, San Luis Obispo, CA (Attn: Kimberly Gonzalez)

California Department of Fish and Game, Gilroy, CA (Attn: Margaret Roper)

LITERATURE CITED

- Bury, R.B. and J.A. Whelan. 1984. Ecology and management of the bullfrog. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Resource Publication 155. 23 pp.
- California Department of Fish and Game. 1997. Recovery Workshop Summary: South Bay Area serpentine plants. Plant conservation Program, California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, California.
- California Natural Diversity Data Base. 1996. Natural Heritage Division. California Department of Fish and Game. State of California.
- Cogswell, H.L. 1956. Spring migration: April 1 to May 31, 1956. Audubon Field Notes 10: 358-363.
- Corelli, T. 1991. A Petition to the State of California Fish and Game Commission to list Coyote Ceanothus (*Ceanothus ferrisiae*). 7 pp.
- Cutler, B.D. and E.A. Pugh. 1959. Nesting season: June 1 to August 15, 1959. Audubon Field Notes 13: 450-454.
- DeGroot, D.S. 1927. The California clapper rail: its nesting habitats, enemies, and habitat. Condor. 29:259-270.
- Ehrlich, P.R., R.R. White, M.C. Singer, S.W. McKechnie, and L.E. Gilbert. 1975. Checkerspot butterflies: a historical perspective. Science 188: 221-228.
- Emlen, S.T. 1977. "Double clutching" and its possible significance in the bullfrog. Copeia 1977(4):749-751.
- Garcia, E.J. 1995. Conservation of the California clapper rail: An analysis of survey methods and habitat use in Marin County, California. M.Sci. Thesis, University of California-Davis. 135 pp.
- Foerster, K.S., and J.E. Takekawa. 1991. San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge predator management plan and final environmental assessment. San Francisco Bay NWR, Newark, CA. 54 pp.
- Foerster, K.S., J.E. Takekawa, and J.D. Albertson. 1990. Breeding density, nesting habitat, and predators of the California clapper rail. Unpubl. Rpt. No. SFBNWR-116400-90-1, prep. for San Francisco Bay NWR, Newark, CA. 46 pp.
- Gill, R., Jr. 1972. South San Francisco Bay breeding bird survey, 1971. Wildlife Management Branch Administrative Report 72-6. Sacramento, CA. 69 pp.

- Goldwasser, S. 1981. Habitat requirement of the least Bell's vireo. California Department of Fish and Game Final Report, Job IV-38.1.
- Gray, M.V., and J. Greaves. 1981. The Riparian Forest as Habitat for the Least Bell's Vireo. Pp. 605-611 in R. Warner and K. Hedrix, Eds. California Riparian Systems: Ecology, Conservation and Productive Management. University of California Press, Davis, California.
- Grinnell, J., H.D. Bryant, and T.I. Storer. 1918. The game birds of California. University of California Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, Berkeley, CA. pp. 473-478.
- Hammond, P.C. 1986. A rebuttal to the Arnold classification of *Speyeria callippe* (Nymphalidae) and defense of the subspecies concept. J. Res. Lep. 24(3):197-208.
- Hammond, P.C., and D.V. McCorkle. 1984. The decline and extinction of *Speyeria* populations resulting from human environmental disturbances (Nymphalidae:Argynninae). J. Res. Lep. 22(4):217-224.
- Harding, E.K., D.F. Doak, J. Albertson, and J.E. Takekawa. 1998. Predator management in San Francisco Bay wetlands: past trends and future strategies. Final Report prepared for U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, CA.
- Harrison, S., D.D. Murphy, and P.R. Ehrlich. 1988. Distribution of the bay checkerspot butterfly, *Euphydryas editha bayensis*: evidence for a metapopulation model. American Naturalist 132: 360-382.
- Harvey, T.E. 1980. A breeding season survey of the California clapper rail in south San Francisco Bay, California. Unpubl. Final Rpt. prep. for San Francisco Bay NWR, Newark, CA. 45 pp.
- Hayes, M.P. and M.R. Jennings. 1988. Habitat correlates of distribution of the California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) and the foothill yellow-legged frog (*Rana boylei*): Implications for management. Pages 144-158 In: R. Sarzo, K. E. Severson, and D. R. Patton (technical coordinators). Proceedings of the Symposium on the Management of Amphibians, Reptiles, and Small Mammals in North America. U.S.D.A. Forest Service General Technical Report RM-166.
- Hayes, M.P. and M.M. Miyamoto. 1984. Biochemical, behavioral and body size differences between *Rana aurora aurora* and *R. a. draytonii*. Copeia 1984(4):1018-1022.
- Hayes, M.P. and M.R. Tennant. 1985. Diet and feeding behavior of the red-legged frog, (*Rana aurora draytonii*) (Ranidae). The Southwestern Naturalist 30(4):601-605.
- Hickman, J.C. 1993. The Jepson Manual. University of California Press, Berkeley, California. 1400 pp.

- Huenneke, L.F., S.P. Hamburg, R. Koide, H.A. Mooney, and P.M. Vitousek. 1990. Effects of soil resources on plant invasion and community structure in Californian serpentine grassland. *Ecology* 71: 478-491.
- Hunter, J.C. 1989. Report to the Fish and Game Commission on the status of Tiburon indian paintbrush (*Castilleja neglecta*). Natural Heritage Division, California Department of Fish and Game. Status Report 89-12.
- Jennings, M.R. 1988. Natural history and decline of native ranids in California. Pages 61-72. *In*: H.F. DeLisle, P.R. Brown, B. Kaufman, and B.M. McGurty (editors). Proceedings of the conference on herpetology. Southwestern Herpetologists Society, Special Publication (4):1-143.
- Jennings, M.R. and M.P. Hayes. 1985. Pre-1900 overharvest of red-legged frogs (*Rana aurora draytonii*): The inducement for bullfrog (*Rana catesbeiana*) introduction. *Herpetologica* 41(1):94-103.
- Jennings, M.R. and M.P. Hayes. 1990. Status of the red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) in the Pescadero Marsh Natural Preserve. Report prepared for the Department of Parks and Recreation, Sacramento, California. 30 pp. + Tables and Figures.
- Jennings, M.R., M.P. Hayes, and D.C. Holland. 1992. A petition to the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service to place the red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) and the western pond turtle (*Clemmys marmorata*) on the list of endangered and threatened wildlife and plants. 21 pp.
- Kruse, K.C. and M.G. Francis. 1977. A predation deterrent in larvae of the bullfrog, *Rana catesbeiana*. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* 106(3):248-252.
- Launer, A.E., and D.D. Murphy. 1994. Umbrella species and the conservation of habitat fragments: a case of a threatened butterfly and a vanishing grassland ecosystem. *Biological Conservation* 69: 145-153.
- Linsdale, J.M. 1951. Spring migration: April 1 to May 31, 1951. *Audubon Field Notes* 5:273-274.
- Mattoon, S.O., R.D. Davis, and O.D. Spencer. 1971. Rearing techniques for species of *Speyeria* (Nymphalidae). *J. Lep. Soc.* 25:247-256.
- Mayer, M.S., P.S. Soltis, and D.E. Soltis. 1994. The evolution of the *Streptanthus glandulosus* complex (Cruciferae): Genetic divergence and gene flow in serpentine endemics. *American Journal of Botany* 81: 1288-1299.

McCarten. 1992. Petition to the State of California Fish and Game Commission: *Streptanthus albidus* ssp. *albidus*.

McMinn, H.E. 1933. Two new species of *Ceanothus* from California. *Madroño* 2: 89-90.

Murphy, D.D. 1988. The Kirby Canyon conservation agreement: a model for the resolution of land-use conflicts involving threatened invertebrates. *Environmental Conservation* 15: 45-48.

Murphy, D.D., and S.B. Weiss. 1988. Ecological studies and the conservation of the bay checkerspot butterfly, *Euphydryas editha bayensis*. *Biological Conservation* 46: 183-200.

Munz, P.A., and D.D. Keck. 1959. A California flora. University of California Press, Berkeley.

Orsak, L.J. 1980. The endangered San Francisco silverspot butterfly of California. Dept. of Zoology and Physiology, Univ. of Wyoming, Laramie, Wyoming. 4pp.

Page, G.W. and L.E. Stenzel (eds.). 1981. The breeding status of the snowy plover in California. *Western Birds* 12(1):1-40.

Powell, A.N., J.M. Terp, C.L. Collier, and B.L. Peterson. 1997. The status of western snowy plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) in San Diego County, 1997. Report to the California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, CA, and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Carlsbad, CA, and Portland, OR. 34 pp.

Regional Environmental Consultants (RECON). 1989. Comprehensive Species Management Plan for the Least Bell's Vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*). Prepared for San Diego Association of Governments, San Diego, California.

Ryan, T.P. and J.L. Parkin. 1998. The western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) in southern San Francisco Bay. Summary of detections made during colonial waterbird monitoring surveys from 1981 to 1997. Prepared for Santa Clara Valley Water District, San Jose, CA. 19 pp.

Sibley, C.G. 1952. The birds of the south San Francisco Bay region. Unpubl. manuscript.

Smith, E.W., and E. Smith. 1947. Another field trip report. Bulletin of the Santa Clara Valley Audubon Society. Vol. 1-2.

Thomas Reid Associates. 1992. Final Report to the San Mateo County Steering Committee for San Bruno Mountain. Endangered Species Survey San Bruno Mountain. Biological Study--1980-1981. Thomas Reid Associates, Palo Alto, California.

- Thomas Reid Associates, and D.D. Murphy. 1987. Kirby Canyon Landfill conservation plan 1985/1986 monitoring report. Prepared for Kirby Canyon Conservation Trustees, February 17, 1987. Unpublished.
- Ryan, T.R. and J.L. Parkin. 1988. The western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) in southern San Francisco Bay: summary of detections made during colonial waterbird monitoring surveys from 1981 to 1997. San Francisco Bay Bird Observatory report to the Santa Clara Valley Water District.
- Salata, L. 1981. Least Bell's Vireo Reserch, Camp Pendleton Marine Copsr. Base, San Diego County, California 1981. Unpublished Report, Natural Resorces Office, Camp Pendleton, California.
- Santa Clara Valley Water District. 2001. Revised Stream Maintentnace togram Biologicval Assessment. Santa Clara Valley Water District, San Jose, California. 71 pp. + appendices.
- Smith, E. 1955. Seasonal observations. *Avocet* 2:25-26.
- Stebbins, R.C. 1985. A field guide to western reptiles and amphibians. Houghton Mifflin Company, Boston, Massachusetts. xiv + 336 pp.
- Stenzel, L.E., J.C. Warriner, J.S. Warriner, K.S. Wilson, F.C. Bidstrup, and G.W. Page. 1994. Long-distance breeding dispersal of snowy plovers in western North America. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 63:887-902.
- Storer, T.I. 1925. A synopsis of the amphibia of California. University of California Publications in Zoology 27:1-342.
- Storer, T.I. 1933. Frogs and their commercial use. *Fish and Game* 19(3):203-213.
- Twedt, B. 1993. A comparative ecology of *Rana aurora* Baird and Girard and *Rana catesbeiana* Shaw at Freshwater Lagoon, Humboldt County, California. Unpubl. M.S. California State University-Humboldt, Arcata, California. 53 pp + appendix.
- U.S. Army Corps of Engineers. 2000. Biological data report for proposed modification to the Guadalupe River Project downtown San Jose, California. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Sacramento District.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 1987. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; determination of threatened status for the bay checkerspot butterfly (*Euphydryas editha bayensis*). *Federal Register* 52: 35366-35378 (September 18, 1987).

- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 1994. Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Designation of Critical Habitat for the Least Bell's Vireo. Final rule. Federal Register 59:4845-4867.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 1995. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; determination of endangered status for ten plants and threatened status for two plants from serpentine habitats in the San Francisco Bay region of California. Federal Register 60 (23): 6671-6685.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 1998. Recovery Plan for Serpentine Soil Species of the San Francisco Bay Area. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon. 431 pp.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 1998b. Draft Recovery Plan for the Least Bell's Vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*). U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon. 139 pp.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2000. Draft Recovery Plan for the red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*). U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon. 258 pp.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2000a. Code of Federal Register 65 FR 54891. Proposed Designation of Critical Habitat for the Red-Legged Frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*); Proposed Rule. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2001. Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) Pacific Coast Population Draft Recovery Plan. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon. 228 pp.+ appendices.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2001a. Code of Federal Register 66 FR 21449. Designation of Critical Habitat for the Bay Checkerspot Butterfly (*Euphydryas editha bayensis*); Final Rule. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon. 40 pp.
- Warriner, J.S., J.C. Warriner, G.W. Page, and L.E. Stenzel. 1986. Mating system and reproductive success of a small population of polygamous snowy plovers. Wilson Bull. 98(1):15-37.
- Weiss, S.B. 1996. Weather, landscape structure, and the population ecology of a threatened butterfly, *Euphydryas editha bayensis*. Ph.D. dissertation, Stanford University, Stanford, California. 119 pp.
- Weiss, S.B. 1999. Cars, cows, and checkerspot butterflies: nitrogen deposition and management of nutrient-poor grasslands for a threatened species. Conservation Biology 13:1476-1486.

- Williams, L. 1957. Spring migration: April 1 to May 31, 1957. Audubon Field Notes 11:373-375.
- Wilson, R.A. 1980. Snowy plover nesting ecology on the Oregon coast. MS Thesis, Oregon State University, Corvallis. 41 pp.
- Wright, A.H. and A.A. Wright. 1949. Handbook of frogs and toads of the United States and Canada. Comstock Publishing Company, Inc., Ithaca, New York. xii + 640 pp.
- Zucca, J.J. 1954. A study of the California clapper rail. Wasmann Journal of Biology. 12(2): 135-153.

In Litt. References

- Barry, S., 1992. Letter to Marvin L. Plenert, Regional Director, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon regarding proposed listing of the California red-legged frog.
- Freas, K. 1993. Letter to Field Supervisor, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 2 pp.
- Hunt, L. 1993. Letter to Peter C. Sorensen, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland Oregon regarding proposed listing of the California red-legged frog.
- Mayall, D. 1996. Letter to Diane Elam, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 2 pp.
- Mayer, M. 1998. Letter to Wayne White, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 1 p.
- McCarten, N. 1998. Letter to Wayne White, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 5 pp. and attachments.
- Schmidt, C. 1996. Letter to Diane Elam, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 2 pp.
- Schmidt, C. 1998. Letter to Wayne White, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California. 3 pp.